

GOOD PRACTICES & RESEARCH INNOVATION COLLECTED - PF

ADVISOR NETWORK FOR OPTIMAL FERTILISERS USE

Practice PF n° 1

SOILEXACT: THE USE OF SOIL MOISTURE SENSORS TO OPTIMIZE IRRIGATION AND SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT TO IMPROVE MINERAL UPTAKE AND CROP GROWTH

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Soil moisture sensing, irrigation

#PF, Food, Food, Fibre, Feed, Oil, Vegetables, GP, The Netherlands

Short description

- ➔ Soil moisture sensors can measure soil moisture content. Growers use that information, for example, to prioritize irrigation of fields: which ones should be irrigated first, which can wait? This is especially important in situations where the fields of a farmer are spread over a wider region. There the transport and start of the irrigation set is a limiting factor in farm management, it might even be impossible to irrigate all fields that need it. Furthermore, optimal irrigation is needed for optimal uptake of minerals by plants. If uptake is not optimized, growth is affected plus minerals stay in the cultivation layer and may leach in case of heavy rainfall or in case of excessive irrigation (double negative effect!).
- ➔ So, soil moisture has a strong direct and indirect effect on the profitability and sustainability of fertilizer management. A specific challenge for soil sensors is to install them in a way that they are representative for the field in which they are situated. The soil around the sensors should have a good connection, but not too firm; they should not be installed in a border and also not in places where the machines can destroy them. To cope with these challenges, different designs are available; mostly

complex and expensive but also swarms of small sensors are under development. In the next years possibilities will expand, giving new impulses for precision agriculture.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The majority of farmers fertilise and irrigate traditionally. When fertilisation takes place in dry periods, shortly after fertilising, irrigation will take place to stimulate mineral absorption.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Farmers don't really know when they need to start irrigation.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Soil moisture sensors are here for a couple of years. But the cost benefits are somewhat hard to compare. When it is dry farmers just need to irrigate and in those moments soil sensors are not really useful. But when it is starting to get dry you might have an advantage when you use a sensor.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Some work with 4G or 5G networks, others use Bluetooth. Some kind of digital communication is needed.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** No.
- **Additional requirements for application:** You will need a software platform which provides you the results of the sensors.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** The data is mostly used for irrigation, but it also can be useful for other precision farming applications. Or when you have to start demonstrating as a matter of policy why crops were irrigated.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Influence on soil quality:** Increased, as water is given by need.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, chalky, loamy, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment,
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fuel, skilled labor
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Using sensors allows you to make better irrigation choices in the longer term because the underlying data supports your choice. Better irrigation will improve uptake of minerals by plants.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** If irrigation is optimized, it ensures that the nutrients present are better absorbed by the crop. Too much or too little water causes nutrients to leach out.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** The purchase of sensors is not subsidized.
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Local irrigation policies may prevent certain crops from being grown in certain areas in the future. Farmers in these regions will be less likely to invest in these techniques.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes, precision farming is supported by Eco-schemes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** dust
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, the use of technical innovations to reduce losses contribute to a better image for the industry.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, when the farmer becomes more in control of his water use it can lead to greater self-satisfaction.

Contact

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Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Source of information <https://www.proeftuinprecisielandbouw.nl/vergelijkingstest-met-negen-bodemvochtsensoren/>

Additional info/links:

<https://www.proeftuinprecisielandbouw.nl/vergelijkingstest-met-negen-bodemvochtsensoren/>

Practice PF n° 2

ADVANCED NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT USING SOIL ANALYSIS AND GROWTH SIMULATION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Crop growth modelling, Data-driven fertilization

#PF, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, GP, The Netherlands

Short description

- ➔ To optimise crop growth throughout the season, it is important to offer the right amount of fertiliser to the crop at the right time. In The Netherlands several institutes offer a method that combines soil samples and crop growth modelling to optimize crop yield while minimizing the environmental impact.
- ➔ The method works by collecting soil samples to assess the current available nutrients. These samples are combined with crop-specific growth models to simulate plant development and nutrient demand. These models account for factors such as planting date and soil type and give advice about the amount of nutrients a farmer should give till the end of the grow season.
- ➔ This integration enhances decision-making by providing a comprehensive overview of nutrient management practices. For example, a farmer uses a standard fertilizer at the beginning of the growing season, which consists mainly of slurry. During the growing season, an additional soil sample provides the optimal amount of fertilizer. The main benefits of applying this practice are:
 - a) By optimizing fertilization this method can help farmers achieve higher yields and better crop quality.
 - b) Precise nutrient application minimizes the risk of nitrogen leaching and emissions of greenhouse gases.
 - c) By applying only the necessary amount of fertilizer, farmers can reduce input costs.
 - d) This practice helps farmers comply with strict nitrate regulations by providing data-driven recommendations.
- ➔ A real example comes from a potato farmer in a region with sandy soils. This method uses extra soil

samples, and crop growth models to determine that 50 kg N/ha is needed at a specific time. By following this recommendation, the farmer can optimize nitrogen use, reduce environmental impact, and maximize wheat yield. By leveraging advanced technology and data-driven insights, this method empowers farmers to make informed decisions about nitrogen fertilization, leading to more sustainable and profitable agriculture.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? In this region, the standard practice for fertilization is a standardized fertilizer plan. This typically involves applying uniform fertilizer rates across entire fields based on general crop requirements and past experiences. While this approach is straightforward and widely used, it often fails to account for variations in soil nutrient levels, weather conditions, and crop growth patterns within a field.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? In the Netherlands nitrate regulations are quite strict so farmers needed ways to have more control to adjust the amount of fertilizer they use during the season.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: These extra samples are used in horticulture crops for years, with the rising cost of fertilisers around the world. Arable crop farmers started to use these samples more often.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Soil sampling adheres to strict protocols, enforced by samplers from different laboratories. Sample plots are typically limited to 5 hectares. While all measurements are currently manual, automation through robotics or drones is a promising avenue for future operations.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** On its own, this method does not contribute to precision agriculture. However, through additional sampling, farmers can optimize their fertilization practices. In combination with satellite imagery, for example, this method enables site-specific fertilization, adjusting the amount of fertilizer based on the local growth needs of the crop.
- **Additional requirements for application:** no.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** This technique is a helpful addition to the fertiliser plan
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, oil, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** To be improved, as manure will be given upon needs of the crop.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, fertilizers, fuel, internet/data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** skilled labour, fertilizers, fuel,
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** You can use less fertilizer in

some cases. Other long-term benefits are less risks in nutrients losses to ground- and surface water, this method also contributes to a farmer's accountability for why he fertilizes his crops.

- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** It reduces the risk of leaching all nutrients.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Not what we can see.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, avoiding leaching nutrients. Knowledge based farming, precision farming.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, the farmer might save cost on fertilisers without losing yield. Additionally, adopting innovative and sustainable practices like the Bijmestmonitor fosters a sense of pride in using modern technology to achieve both economic and environmental goals.

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Find out more

Source of information <https://www.eurofins-agro.com/nl-nl/bijmestmonitor>

Additional info/links:

<https://www.eurofins-agro.com/nl-nl/bijmestmonitor> ; https://www.eurofins-agro.com/uploads/downloads/NL_Artemis/Fact_Sheet_BijmestMonitor.pdf (not available in English, just translate in your browser)

Practice PF n° 3

ZERO SPOTS METHOD TO OPTIMIZE WHEAT NITROGEN FERTILIZATION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Optimize nitrogen fertilization, variable rate application (VRA)

#PF, Food, feed, Winter wheat, industrial, GP, Sweden

Calibrate Zero spots against the field and make a VRA file

Short description

→ The zero spot fertilization method for wheat is based on the following principles: The nitrogen supply to the wheat during the growing season is done in three steps. 1) The first application in early spring at the time of the start of wheat growth (BBCH30 (middle of March) about 25-40% of the estimated total nitrogen intake. 2) The main application, 40-55% of the estimated total nitrogen intake, is applied at BBCH 30 (middle of April) so that it is available when shooting at BBCH32. 3) The final supplementary application is made in the flag leaf stage at BBCH39) (middle of May). The final supplementary amount of Nitrogen is calculated according to the result of the measuring of the Zero spots. The zero spot is defined as a square area of 3x4 meters within the field that has not been subjected to the application of nitrogen fertilizer. The supplementary rate is distributed according to biomass from satellites.

- The total nitrogen requirement is calculated after the zero spots have been evaluated and revealed the soil's nitrogen supply. The nitrogen requirement is calculated according to 3 different formulas depending on the winter wheat variety and on the final use of the wheat. The winter wheat varieties are classified into three categories based on protein content at optimal nitrogen levels: 1) Low protein wheat (<10% protein) at optimum, 2) Medium protein wheat (10-12% protein) at optimum and 3) High protein wheat (>12% protein) at optimum. In addition, the nitrogen calculation is adapted according to the use of the wheat. A) Own feed and bread wheat 22 kg N/tons harvest, B) Feed for industrial and starch wheat medium or high protein varieties 20 kg N/tons harvest. C) feed for industry and starch wheat Low protein wheat 15 kg N/tons harvest.
- In practice, non-fertilized zero spots for nitrogen are laid out in the fields in the spring in connection with nitrogen fertilization of the winter wheat. At each nitrogen fertilization, it is ensured that the zero spots do not get any nitrogen. When wheat approaches BBCH39, measurements of nitrogen uptake are made in the zero spots. Nitrogen uptake is measured indirectly with Yara's N-tester and via image analysis in Yara's Atfarm app. The values from the measurement are then entered into a formula developed by Yara, where the characteristics of the variety and the use of the wheat is also taken into account as described above. In the formula, the farmer also specifies the estimated harvest and previous fertilization. In this way, the supplemental nitrogen requirement is determined. The supplemental requirement is then used as a basis for determining the optimal distribution of the nitrogen application based on Satellite data via Atfarm or Cropsat.
- In these programs, the value from the zero box is calibrated against the satellite images so that the zero box represents the correct part of the field. Then a VRA file is created and the farmers spread their supplementary application based on the VRA (Variable Rate Application) file.
- By laying two zero spots when spreading organic fertilizer (one that only gets organic fertilizer and one that gets no nitrogen at all), we also have the opportunity to calculate the contribution of the organic fertilizer and remove it from the need for supplementation. This is done by measuring the nitrogen uptake in both zero spots.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Most farmers use 3 nitrogen applications in much the same way as in the zero-spot method. But the nitrogen level is determined based on experience from previous years and the fertilization that was carried out last winter.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The background to the method was that traditional field experiments with nitrogen fertilization only gave the answer about the optimal strategy after harvest. There were no tools available to evaluate the nitrogen requirement during the wheat growing season and be able to adjust the nitrogen application during the growing season based on the crop needs and variation in the field. Nitrogen fertilization experiments were analyzed to look for correlations that could explain the difference in nitrogen requirements at different sites with the same harvest. These analyses showed that these differences could be explained by the soil's nitrogen delivery capacity which could be measured using nitrogen Zero spots. At the same time, a new series of experiments was started that looked at nitrogen fertilization for specific varieties. These experiments showed that the Swedish wheat varieties can be divided into 3 groups depending on the protein content in the kernel at optimal nitrogen application. These studies also led us new calculation tools based on the characteristics of the variety, the final use of the wheat, and the expected yield and soil nitrogen delivery capacity. We have then also linked these methods with the possibility of using satellite-based biomass maps to account for variations in the field and apply the final nitrogen application as a variable rate application based on crop needs rather than a uniform average dose.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Zero spot method is the result of knowledge built up over several years. It took about 10 years from the time the evaluating nitrogen fertilization experiments started until a method useful for farmers was developed. Once the method was developed, it was relatively quick to put it into practice and to get farmers and advisors interested in the method. In the beginning, they measured with a handheld N sensor in 2015. But this was very time-consuming, and one single sensor had to travel around with one person to take measurements at several farms. Since 2015, other indirect methods have been tested to measure nitrogen delivery. For example, measuring straw length using image analysis to see if we could find an easier method to measure the nitrogen uptake. The aim was to come to a method farmers could manage themselves. 2024 was the first year we were able to offer a method where the farmers themselves can measure nitrogen uptake in their own zero spots without being dependent on anyone having to come out and measure with him. So that development has taken 9 years. The knowledge of nitrogen need per variety type has been evaluated in trials since 2013. But it only took 2 years before we could see correlations which we were able to implement in the method in 2015. Since then, the trial series has remained until 2022. So that we could evaluate and be sure that the results were right. During these years we have fine-tuned the system to be better. From 2025 all the steps in deciding the Nitrogen uptake can be managed in Atfarm (at. Farm, Yara).

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The method is applicable for farmers or advisors having access to N-tests and Yara's Atfarm in order to be able to measure and evaluate the Zero spots. Previously, a hand-held N-sensor was used, with the challenge that it had to be moved around to measure different fields in a large area in a very short time, which was a major logistical problem. For the farmer to take part in the information of the nitrogen requirements, all that is required is that the zero spots must be measured to find out the nitrogen needs of the field. Either by the farmer with the Zero spots method or by an advisory organization. To utilize the method optimally, the farmer needs a fertilizer spreader that can spread VRA task maps and access to computer programs that can create VRA task maps based on biomass. In Sweden, common examples are Yara's Atfarm and Cropsat.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** The VRA task map is generated in ATFARM based on satellite images and implemented in the spreader computer or GPS equipment in the tractor. The ease of implementation and the quality depends on the equipment in the tractor. But mostly issues can be easily fixed the first time they want to apply a variable rate application.
- **Additional requirements for application:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** The method is viable in other cereals. The important thing is to understand the correlation between optimal nitrogen levels and soil nitrogen delivery. The method is tested in Malt barley where there are more factors than the soil's nitrogen delivery capacity that must be taken into account to get a reliable value. Unfortunately, there is no model that works in Malt barley, yet There are some small tests

in Hybrid rye and Autumn barley. There are currently tests at farm level in Lay. The zero spots are good at showing the soil's nitrogen delivery capacity in the crop.

- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** No
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, fuel, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** improved water quality, higher yield, better quality, optimized and reduced fertilizer use.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Nitrogen leaching decreases.
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** digestate, animal manure, agricultural residues, municipal sludge, compost

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No not in Sweden
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Not what we can see.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No not in Sweden
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes. The environmental benefits from this practice should contribute to a better public image and at the same time it contributes to a better quality and quantity of the yield. Because the method optimizes the use of Nitrogen to get the optimal yield and quality with the right amount of Nitrogen. This will minimize Nitrogen leaching to the Baltic Sea which is a major concern in Sweden.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes. The environmental benefit from this practice gives the farmer a sense of accomplishment of doing something good at the same time they will improve their own economics.

Contact

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Hushållningssällskapet

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Eu member state: Sweden

Find out more

Source of information The method has been developed by Yara and Hushållningssällskapet in a collaborative project which started in 2015. The Zero spots method has been in use since 2016, with yearly updates and improvements and the practical use of the method is increasing (about 30% of the Hushållningssällskapet clients are using this method).

Additional info/links:

Professional magazine.

Arvensis 2015-08-01, Sortanpassa kvävegödslingen, Mattias Hammarstedt HIR Skåne

Arvensis 2018-01-01, Vetegödslingen ska styras efter sort och avsättning, Mattias Hammarstedt HIR Skåne.

Arvensis 2021-02-01, Nollrutor ett måste för rätt kvävegiva, Patrik Svanström HIR Skåne

Arvensis 2024-04-29, Verktyg inför kompletteringsgivan i höstvete, Frida Lindell HIR Skåne

Växtpressen nr1, 2018. Ny indelning i Sortyper avgör sortval och N-gödsling, Mattias Hammarstedt HIR Skåne och Anpassade kvävegivor fungerar, Katarina Elfström och Carl Magnus Olsson YARA.

https://issuu.com/yarasverige/docs/v_xtpressen_yara_20181

Växtpressen nr1, 2016. Nya N-rekommendationer i vete, Ingemar Gruveaus, Yara

https://issuu.com/yarasverige/docs/va_xtpressen1601_low

Växtpressen nr1, 2020, Handfasta råd inför 2020, Magnus Jeppsson, Yara

Pod

Växtpressenpodden: Tid för kompletteringsgödsling, <https://vaxtpressenpod.libsyn.com/tid-fr-kompletteringsgdsling>

Practice PF n° 4

USE OF MOBILE APPS AND SATELLITE IMAGES TO IDENTIFY FERTILISATION NEEDS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#satellite imagery, mobile apps

#PF, GP, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Ornamental, Industrial, Slovenia

Short description

→ This practice describes the use of available satellite images to monitor actual crop status and act quickly on it. This helps to use fertiliser inputs more efficiently and reduce costs. Variable rate fertiliser prescription maps are traditionally based on soil samples of a given area. The aim of this new approach is to optimize fertiliser use, reduce costs and at the same time increase the efficiency of fertilization using crop information acquired from satellite images. Satellite images make it possible to retrieve information on the state of agricultural areas in a global level. These images can be used

so that farmers, researchers and agronomists can monitor plant growth, assess field conditions and identify potential problems that affect the quantity and quality of crops. With the latest development of satellite technology, images have become increasingly accurate and more accessible, making it easier to use them in agricultural practice. A significant advantage is the speed with which information on the situation of crops in the field can be obtained so that the farmer can react immediately with the application of appropriate fertilisers at the right location.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Standard practice is to calculate fertilizer application rate based on soil and plant analyses, use a fertiliser plan and apply the same amount over and over again, regardless of soil and plant variability.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Cost of investment in technology, especially on smaller farms

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 3 - 5

years

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Improving and introducing precision farming equipment (tractor with GPS, variable rate fertilizer technology) and dedicated software to process satellite images and generate fertilizer prescription maps (One soil, Nextfarming, PIX4Dfields, etc.).
- **Additional requirements for application:** Amount of investment, compatibility of the machinery with the technology.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** The technology can be used in several areas or sectors of agriculture.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Very high impact on soil quality.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** unskilled labour, skilled labour, fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, fuel, transportation, land, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Reduction of production costs, reduction of the cost price of the product.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** More efficient and targeted use of nutrients (P2O5, K2O, N). Reduced consumption with higher production.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** digestate, animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** There is no relevant legislation on the use of drones.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** concerns about data breaches, change of the landscape
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, it decreases the groundwater pollution.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, because of many reasons: environmental, economic, exemplary function for others.

Contact

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Eu member state: Slovenia

Find out more

Source of information Publications in agricultural journals and scientific articles

Additional info/links:

VINDIŠ, Peter. Izdelava digitalne karte variabilnega založnega gnojenja kmetijskih kultur na podlagi analize tal. Kmetovalec : strokovna kmetijska revija. April 2024, letn. 92, št. 4, str. 24-25, ilustr. ISSN 1318-4245. [COBISS.SI-ID 190438659]

VINDIŠ, Peter. Pametni trosilniki mineralnih gnojil za variabilno gnojenje. Kmetovalec : strokovna kmetijska revija.

Oktober 2024, letn. 92, št. 10, str. 9-11, ilustr. ISSN 1318-4245. [COBISS.SI-ID 208829955] VINDIŠ, Peter. Uporaba satelitske slike in NDVI indeksa za dognojevanje kmetijskih kultur. Kmetovalec : strokovna kmetijska revija. februar 2024, letn. 92, št. 2, str. 6-7, ilustr. ISSN 1318-4245. [COBISS.SI-ID

183873027]

VINDIŠ, Peter. Variabilna setev kmetijskih kultur. Kmetovalec : strokovna kmetijska revija. Junij 2024, letn. 92, št. 6, str. 11-12, ilustr. ISSN 1318-4245. [COBISS.SI-ID 196921347]

Practice PF n° 5

DEVELOPING PRECISE FERTILISATION PLANS WITH REGARD TO VRA USING SATELLITE IMAGERY AND DRONES IN MAIZE AND CEREALS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, NDVI maps

#PF, GP, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Ornamental, Industrial, Slovenia

Short description

- ➔ Satellite images are particularly suited for crops such as cereals, maize, and other field crops, as their scale aligns with the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. These images, combined with drone technology, provide essential data for implementing Variable Rate Application (VRA) of fertilizers, a core practice in precision farming. Optical satellites and drones equipped with multispectral sensors capture high-resolution imagery and vegetation indices, such as NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) and NDRE (Normalized Difference Red Edge Index). These indices help identify field zones that exhibit variability in crop health, growth, or nutrient requirements. Such zones often require further targeted monitoring or additional measurements, such as nitrate levels or soil sampling.
- ➔ To make fieldwork easier and more efficient, farmers use a dedicated mobile app developed as part of the EIP Precision Farming and Digitalisation project. This app provides field maps that guide users to specific zones for collecting measurements or observations. For example, a farmer can navigate the app to underperforming zones identified by the satellite imagery, enter real-time soil nitrate test

results, and input other observations directly into the system. The ability to combine remote sensing data with ground-truthed measurements ensures that the analysis is as accurate and reliable as possible.

- ➔ Agronomists then analyze the combined data to generate targeted fertilization recommendations based on the actual nutrient needs of the crops. These recommendations are used to create a digital fertilization plan. Farmers transfer these files to their equipment using USB drives, cloud-based systems, or wireless connections, ensuring seamless integration of data.
- ➔ The integration of satellite imagery, drone-based data collection, soil measurements, and precision machinery enhances the accuracy of fertilizer application. The ability to combine this information with potential soil analysis results allows for a comprehensive understanding of both plant and soil needs. For example, satellite imagery highlights crop health variability, while soil analysis confirms nutrient deficiencies, enabling farmers to tailor fertilizer applications even more precisely.
- ➔ By using VRA technology, farmers achieve multiple benefits, including improved crop yields, reduced fertilizer costs, and minimized environmental impact. Precision application prevents over-fertilization in healthy zones and provides additional nutrients to underperforming areas, resulting in uniform crop growth and better resource use. This practice not only enhances productivity but also supports sustainable farming practices by reducing nutrient leaching, protecting water quality, and minimizing greenhouse gas emissions.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? In this region, most farmers use conventional fertilisation with one dose per whole area. This rate is determined by feel, according to the recommended and allowed annual nitrogen rate per plant. This traditional approach often leads to over- or under-fertilization in different parts of the field, resulting in inefficient nutrient use, environmental impacts, and yield variability. Few farmers draw up a nitrogen fertilisation plan based on soil or plant samples taken from the area, and this plan provides for a single fertilisation rate for each individual fertiliser at a particular stage of growth over the whole area.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The main challenge leading to the adoption of VRA is the underutilization of modern mechanization. For example, many farms have VRA-enabled machinery, but they do not yet use this method and still fertilise fields with a uniform amount of fertiliser across the whole field, using the section control function. Because VRA requires in-depth knowledge and a lot of digital skills, farms that use this method mostly turn to experts with specialised knowledge or employ highly trained technologists. VRA offers opportunities for larger farms to save money, increase profitability, and protect natural resources... Smaller farms have a bit different issues like crop levelling, less fertiliser use, especially when fertiliser prices went over the roof, to be part of the project and get the knowledge and learn how to use that knowledge.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: It is estimated that the time needed to implement a new method on a farm is one growing season. It depends a lot on the self-initiative, the technical 'ability' of the farmer. It takes about one growing season to introduce the practice on the farm, because it takes a lot of learning and practice. Monitoring measures are checking satellite images, monitoring fertiliser use, etc.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes, it takes a lot of planning, which is the biggest problem with implementing the VRA. First of all, the farmer has to decide to fertilise each field according to the VRA method. Then it is necessary to review the satellite images, prepare a sampling plan, go to the field to take soil and plant samples, analyse the available nutrients and based on the results, draw up a fertilisation plan. Only then can the farmer import this file into the machinery and carry out the fertilisation. The whole process thus does not have to be done on the basis of the current reading alone, but requires a lot of organisation, negotiation and time due to the multiple steps involved (especially if an external expert is involved, e.g. an agricultural advisor, if the analysis has to be done in a laboratory, etc.). A major challenge here is the dependence on the weather, because sometimes farmers cannot wait to do the job.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Yes, in addition to specialised machinery, the farmer must also use software and apps that allow the review of satellite images, the preparation of a sampling plan, a mobile app to carry out targeted sampling and the preparation of more precise fertilisation plans. If the farm analyses the plant samples itself, it also needs equipment for nitrate tests.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Apps, good internet connection and mechanisation with ISOBUS and navigation systems.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** In addition to precision fertilisation, it can be applied also to precision sowing, harvesting and spraying.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Soil quality is improved, especially when basic fertilisation (e.g. P and K) and precision liming measures are applied. In particular, if the land is heterogeneously stocked before these measures are carried out, then such measures can even out the stocking rate on the surface in the long term. Another positive effect of nitrogen fertilisation is that only as much fertiliser is applied as needed and where it is really needed (i.e. according to the real needs of the plants in a given part of the field). This reduces the possibility of nutrient leaching into groundwater or GHG losses to a minimum.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data subscription costs, energy
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Improved efficiency of mechanization use (more exploited), on-farm savings of reprocessed material.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Very reduced leaching of these elements, because only as much N is applied as the plants in the subsoil actually need and therefore the efficiency of use is increased. P and K are used in order to balance the availability to the optimum.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps

- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Not in principle, just that the CAP measure is not 'precise' enough.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** Yes: Nitrous oxide, Yes: Ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** concerns about data breaches
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** yes, by showcasing environmentally responsible and sustainable farming methods.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, by fostering pride in adopting innovative and sustainable farming techniques.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information <https://www.kgzs-ms.si/precizno-kmetijstvo-in-digitalizacija-za-bolj-trajnostno-pridelavo-poljscin-in-zelenjave/>

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/precision-agriculture-and-digitization-more-sustainable-crop-and-vegetable-production_en

<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61552183976611>

Practice PF n° 6

FERTILISER SPREAD PATTERN MEASUREMENT AND SPREADER ADJUSTMENT USING COLLECTION TRAYS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Fertilizer spread pattern, Spreader adjustment

#PF, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Industrial, GP, Belgium

Short description

- ➔ Optimizing fertilizer inputs in agricultural production systems is seen as an important strategy to reduce their large environmental impact while supplying the world's increasing need for food, fibre and fuel. Centrifugal fertilizer spreaders are by far the most used mineral fertilizer spreaders due to their large working width, small size, low price and their simple and robust design. Although simple in working principle, the spreading process is difficult to control because it depends on various parameters such as the physical properties of the fertilizer particles, wind conditions, spreader settings, etc. Therefore, deviations between the desired and the actual spread pattern can occur in practice, leading to local under- and over-applications and losses out of the field.
- ➔ To assess the spreader performance at farm level and adjust the machine, if necessary, the spread pattern must be determined. The uniformity of the spread pattern is assessed by measuring the single

transverse spread pattern by placing a row of collection trays equipped with anti-reflection grids in the field perpendicular to the driving direction. After collection, material from each tray is weighed and converted into an application rate. Because of their working principle, broadcast fertilizer spreaders generate gauss or trapezoid shaped spread patterns. As a result, the applied dose is higher centrally behind the spreader and decreases towards the sides of the spreading width. Because of this, overlap is necessary between subsequent swaths to achieve a homogeneous distribution.

- Spread uniformity across the swath width is calculated (and expressed as coefficient of variation (CV)) and the optimal swath width (and corresponding application rate) can be determined based on the measured single spread pattern. According to the European standard EN13739 (2003) (1), the CV should not exceed 15%. If an undesirable spread pattern is measured, the next step is to adjust the spreader setup to obtain a more uniform spreading. This can be done, for example, changing the position of the vanes on the disks, height above the ground, position of the orifice, etc. These measurements are mostly performed for mineral fertilizer centrifugal spreaders but are also applicable for pendulum and manure spreaders. Besides the problem of under- and over-application, broadcast fertilizer spreaders have a high risk of spreading beyond the field border because of their large working width and typical spread pattern. To avoid these losses to the environment, different border spreading technologies (e.g. deflector plate, disc-integrated border spreading...) are now available. Using the collection tray method, the performance of these technologies can be tested and optimized further contributing to optimal fertilizer use.
- (1) EN 13739:2003 Agricultural machinery - Solid fertilizer broadcasters and full width distributors - Environmental protection

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? In most cases no check of the spread pattern is performed. Adjustment of the spreader is done following the instructions of the machine manufacturer or a default setting is used.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Poor distribution of the fertilizer leads to yield losses, visible spreading lanes and quality difference within the field. Fertilizer losses out of the field mean economic losses for the farmer, losses to the environment and are bad for the reputation of the farmer.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: ILVO's fertilizer spreader calibration service was established as the result of a 4-year research project and is operational for several years. Due to the large spreading widths, performing spread pattern tests is a very laborious, time-consuming process. Adjusting the spreader needs some operational knowledge combined with trial and error which makes spread pattern measurements quite expensive. In addition, measurements are weather dependent and require a lot of space. Finally, there is no mandatory spreader testing in Europe which is different from sprayers. For these reasons, and despite the clear advantages, the level of implementation by farmers is relatively low. The level of implementation could increase by setting up a (voluntary or mandatory) spreader testing campaign and/or to foresee some subsidies for farmers testing their spreader. Today, there is no direct monitoring. Indirect monitoring is done among others by measuring nitrogen content in soil and surface water.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Availability and transportation of the collection trays. Performing the measurement requires manpower and some operational knowledge. Measurements are weather dependent and require a lot of space where fertiliser application is allowed. The collection tray method can be applied to all models of fertilizer spreaders
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** no
- **Additional requirements for application:** Not for the actual application but the measurements are weather dependent (no rainfall) and require a lot of space. The tests should be carried out on an even, horizontal and hard surface. The air velocity should be less than 2 m/s during the tests. The air humidity should be less than 65 % and the temperature 10 °C to 25 °C.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Solid fertilizer or manure, broadcast spreaders, border spreading in different cultivations
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** A more uniform level of fertilization at the correct dose rate resulting in less over- and under- applications.
- **Suitable soil types:** silty, chalky, loamy, clay, sandy, peaty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** unskilled labour, Storage
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** More accurate spreading along the field borders (because of the better adjustment of the equipment) will limit the need of large fertiliser-free borders along watercourses and improve surface water quality.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** nitrogen: decrease
- Phosphate: decrease
- Potassium: decrease
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** animal manure, compost

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** no
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** no (only fertilizers)
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** The better adjustment of the spreader will reduce the amount of fertilizer that potentially is spread over the border of the

-
- field (e.g. on roads, ditches, ...). This leads to less pollution of roads, ditches... and a better public
- image.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** A uniform crop without spreading lanes is for sure something the farmers like to see.
- **Other relevant information:** This GP is a pre-season adjustment that can be performed for all solid fertilizer types on the farm. So time occupation is of less importance for the farmer.

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Find out more

Source of information Flemish AgrifoodTEF (<https://www.agrifoodtefvlaanderen.be/en/>)

Additional info/links:

<https://www.agrifoodtefvlaanderen.be/en/sectors/geautomatiseerde-testopstelling-voor-kunstmeststrooiers>

Practice PF n° 7

USE OF THE ONLINE INFORMATION PLATFORM WATCHITGROW TO GENERATE TASK MAPS FOR VARIABLE FERTILISER APPLICATIONS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Online data platform, variable rate fertilizer maps

#PF, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Industrial, GP, Belgium

Short description

- ➔ WatchItgrow is an online platform to support farmers in monitoring arable crops and vegetables more efficiently in view of increasing yields, both qualitatively and quantitatively. It is a collaboration platform for everyone in the sector, from growers, contractors and advisors to buyers.
- ➔ WatchItgrow uses various types of data starting with satellite data combined with e.g. weather data, soil data, IoT data and field data provided by the farmer. These data are combined using new technologies such as big data analytics and machine learning to provide farmers with more timely and personalized advice. The platform offers numerous functions. It can be used to store field data: general information such as the variety, planting date, harvest date or more specific information on

application of fertilizers, pesticides, irrigation...As a farmer you decide whether or not you share these data with your advisor, contractor, buyer...

- ➔ WatchITgrow provides information on crop growth and development as observed from satellite images. From the greenness maps you can easily detect variability within your field and compare crops growing on different fields. By monitoring the weather data (temperature and rainfall) you can better assess the risk for production or quality losses at your fields. WatchITgrow also provides yield forecasts for 2 potato varieties, Bintje and Fontane, at field level. Finally, application maps for variable rate planting, irrigation, haulm killing and variable fertilization can be created.
- ➔ To create an application map for variable rate fertilization, different steps are followed. In the first step, the farmer selects the machine that will be used for fertilizing, the type of fertilizer (mineral, organic, compost) and the product(s) that will be applied. You can select one or more products from the list of existing (mineral) fertilizers or you can create your own product. If you choose the latter option, you can add minerals one by one. When adding the product, you are also asked to add the normal dose you would apply to the field, in kg/ha or l/ha. In step 2, by clicking on “Auto dosage”, the normal product dose is distributed over the different zones within the field according to the selected strategy. “Make bad areas better” applies a higher dose of fertilizer to zones with a low greenness index. When you select “Make good areas better” a higher dose will be applied to zones with a high greenness index. If needed, you can still change the dose.
- ➔ To define the zones WatchITgrow uses greenness (fAPAR) images derived from Sentinel-2 satellite images. The Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (fAPAR) is a vegetation indicator that quantifies the fraction of the solar radiation absorbed by live leaves for the photosynthesis activity. It measures only to the green and alive elements of the canopy.
- ➔ The greenness of each pixel in the field is compared with the median greenness of the field and attributed to one of the following 5 classes: <85%, 85-95%, 95-105%, 105-115%, >115% of the median value. In the last step you can enter the name of the application map and, optionally, an advice date for fertilizing. You can download the polygons and the respective fertilizer dose to be applied as a shapefile by clicking on the download button below or you can just save the map you created. These application maps can then be uploaded in the variable rate fertiliser technology.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? A uniform quantity of fertilizer is applied to the field, usually based on a soil sample analysis and advice at parcel level. Variation in soil quality/fertilizer need within the parcel is not taken into account.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? In most agricultural fields, a natural variation in soil quality is observed, which is linked to the yield potential. If the farmer applies a uniform dose of fertilizer on the field, zones with an overdose or underdose will occur. This leads to a low efficiency in fertilizer use. The evolution towards precision agriculture allows this variation to be mapped and managed accordingly. WatchITgrow provides information on crop growth and development as observed from satellite images. From the greenness maps you can easily detect variability within your field and create application maps for variable rate.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: The first version of the WatchITgrow platform was developed within the iPot research project in the period 2014-2016 and was launched in 2016 focusing the field and yield data in potato production. Since then and till today, the tool was continuously improved and expanded with additional crops and modules

including variable fertilization. To promote the use of the platform, Belgian potato farmers could receive a financial bonus from their buyer in 2019 and 2020 when they actively use the WatchITgrow platform to submit field data and actual yields. The platform can be used to monitor fields in Belgium and surrounding countries.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** It concerns a web-based tool that is freely accessible after registration. Internet access is required to use the platform. A connection with other data sources (e.g. weather stations, yield sensors on harvesters...) is possible, but not required. Applying fertilizer using task maps requires the use of machinery supporting variable rate application.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** To apply the task maps, the farmer should have access to machines that support variable dosing. Or alternatively, a contractor can be called in for this purpose. Currently, most of the machinery fleet is not yet equipped with this technology. In addition, a learning curve will have to be gone through in order to start working with the task maps. For example, when loading the task maps, the correct file format and folder structure must be used, which can vary greatly from manufacturer to manufacturer.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Free account on WatchITgrow platform.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** All types of manure and fertilizer in arable crops and vegetables.
- **Targeted crop categories:** feed, food, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Fertilisation is adjusted to differences in soil quality, so over-or under-fertilisation will be limited.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Higher sustainability of the crop production due to higher yields/lower input of fertilizer.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Nitrogen: decrease
 - Phosphate: decrease
 - Potassium: decrease
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** animal manure, compost

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Data privacy and ownership policy.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No

- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** substantial increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Higher yield with lower input of fertilizer is expected, which will lead to a lower environmental footprint of the products. This sustainability is getting more attention from the consumer.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Farmers are proud to work with innovative technologies which contribute to a more sustainable agriculture.

Contact

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Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information WatchITgrow platform (<https://watchitgrow.be/en>)

Practice PF n° 8

CROPSAT - FREE SATELLITE IMAGERY FOR TAILORED NITROGEN FERTILIZATION IN WHEAT

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Optimize nitrogen fertilization, variable rate application (VRA)

#PF, Food, Feed, wheat, Fibre, GP, Sweden

Short description

- ➔ CropSat is a free precision farming tool developed in Sweden that leverages satellite imagery to optimize nitrogen fertilization, particularly for crops like wheat and other cereals. The tool uses Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) data from satellite images captured every 2-5 days to monitor crop growth, biomass, and variability across fields. By providing tailored nitrogen application maps, CropSat ensures more efficient resource use, reducing both costs and environmental impact.
- ➔ The process begins with farmers accessing the user-friendly CropSat web platform, where they can view their fields on an interactive map. The platform highlights variations in vegetation caused by factors such as soil quality, water availability, or nutrient deficiencies. These insights help farmers identify underperforming zones that require targeted fertilizer applications.
- ➔ To create Variable Rate Application (VRA) maps, the user follows these steps:
 - a) Satellite imagery identifies crop health and biomass variability, providing the basis for precise fertilization planning.
 - b) Farmers can generate application maps by selecting the field, crop, and the target nitrogen rate for specific zones. The platform allows users to input parameters like product type (e.g., mineral fertilizers).

- c) Once the VRA map is created, it can be downloaded in ISO-XML or Shapefile format, ensuring compatibility with modern tractor guidance systems and variable rate spreaders.
- d) The task map is uploaded to the tractor's onboard terminal, allowing the equipment to automatically adjust nitrogen application rates in real time. This precision minimizes over-fertilization in healthy zones while providing additional nutrients where needed.
- CropSat has become an essential tool for farmers because it improves yields, promotes sustainability, and reduces fertilizer costs. Unlike traditional methods, where nitrogen is applied uniformly using generalized recommendations, CropSat enables farmers to account for field variability. The approach addresses previous inefficiencies where some zones were over-fertilized, leading to unnecessary expenses and increased nitrogen leaching, while others were under-fertilized, resulting in reduced yields. Compared to alternative technologies like N-sensors, CropSat provides a more affordable and accessible option, as it does not require costly equipment. Additionally, it requires minimal technical expertise, making it suitable for farmers with a basic understanding of digital tools. All that is needed is access to the internet, a compatible variable rate spreader, and a tractor capable of processing task maps.
- In terms of environmental impact, the precision offered by CropSat significantly reduces nitrogen leaching, contributing to improved water quality. This aligns with sustainability goals while enhancing the public image of agriculture. Moreover, the practice allows farmers to improve both crop quality and economic returns, fostering a sense of accomplishment in balancing profitability and environmental stewardship.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? If farmers do not use VRA for their nitrogen application, they use recommended nitrogen rate tables, which correlate with the crop and the expected yield. The same amount of nitrogen is then applied to the whole field without taking into account field variations.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Nitrogen fertiliser is a major expense for farmers and has a negative impact on the environment. A more resource-efficient approach to nitrogen application has both economic and environmental benefits. Previously, nitrogen fertilizer was applied evenly across fields, which led to inefficiencies: some areas received excessive amounts, while others received too little. Alternatively, farmers had to invest in expensive N-sensors. Compared to using satellite imagery, spreading nitrogen more evenly over the field reduces fertiliser costs, gives better and more consistent crop quality and reduces nitrogen emissions.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: The system was developed in 2014-2015 in a collaboration of... There was an earlier version of Cropsat but it was not as user-friendly and accurate. After the development of 2014-2015 Cropsat is integrated and developed by DataVäxt. The use of Cropsat has been gradual since 2015, but by 2024 it is an established part of grain production for cereal farmers.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** To utilize the method, the farmer needs a fertilizer spreader that can spread VRA task maps
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** A tractor that may receive variation map and a spreader that can handle varied rates.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Access to internet

- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** If the farmer uses mineral fertilisers, this practice is useful, but development is ongoing for other types of fertilisers like organic manure.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** No
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Improved water quality, Lower labour intensity, improvement of human skills.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Decrease of nitrogen leaching.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** digestate, animal manure, municipal sludge, compost

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** Yes: Nitrous oxide
- Yes: Ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes. The environmental benefits from this practice should contribute to a better public image at the same time it contributes to better quality and quantity of the yield.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes. The environmental benefit from this practice gives the farmer a sense of accomplishment of doing something good at the same time they will improve their own economics. It's a win-win situation.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information The CropSat platform is a collaboration between Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU), Hushållningssällskapet, DataVäxt AB and Agroväst Livsmedel AB. Financed by Stiftelsen Lantbruksforskning <https://cropsat.com/>

Practice PF n° 9

SITE SPECIFIC ESTIMATION OF WINTER CEREALS AND RAPESEED NITROGEN NEEDS VIA SATELLITE IMAGERY (MES SAT'IMAGES, FARMSTAR)

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Satellite imagery, crop health monitoring

#PF, food, oil, feed, cereals, rapeseed, industrial, GP, France

Short description

→ The theoretical calculation of crop nitrogen needs in France has been carried out since 1992. This calculation is used to comply with the Nitrates Directive (European directive). The necessary data are provided by technical institutes and aggregated through COMIFER (French Committee for the Study and Development of Rational Fertilization). Estimating crop needs using satellite imagery is a major advance in precision agriculture. The images captured reveal information on plant cover (biomass) and allow the modelling of plant nitrogen content (Nitrogen Nutrition Index) to assess plant nitrogen needs and advise farmers on their site-specific fertilization practices for winter cereals and rapeseed. Thanks to spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), farmers can identify areas requiring specific nitrogen inputs. All farmers can use these digital solutions (such as Mes Sat'images and Farmstar) to optimize their fertilization strategy both with solid and liquid fertilisers. Fertilisers can be applied uniformly all over the field using conventional equipment or at different rates in each part of the field using precision farming tools using e.g. the ISOBUS standardized data exchange format (ISOXML). ISOXML facilitates the interoperability between the precision farming tools and software packages such as Farmstar. This optimizes fertilization, thereby reducing costs and minimizing environmental impact. In addition, this approach promotes sustainable resource management, while increasing yields. By integrating satellite imagery into agricultural practices, it becomes possible to respond more precisely to the crop needs, ensuring a more efficient and resilient food production.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Standard practice is to apply the nitrogen balance method (COMIFER Guide to Reasoned Fertilization). Over a given period of time, the mass balance

of the soil mineral nitrogen stock in the crop root zone is written as follows: Final state - Initial state = Inputs - Outputs (e.g. <https://comifer.asso.fr/calcul-de-la-fertilisation-azotee/>)

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Agronomic and economic optimization of nitrogen management (reasoning the inputs to provide the right dose)

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Since 1992, the use of COMIFER gradually increase up to about 1/3 of the winter cereals and rapeseed area in France in 2024 (7 500 000 hectares total)

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** subscription to a paid service (between 9 and 13 € per hectare), plot context (variety of winter cereals with difference nitrogen needs between 2,8 to 3,2 kilogram of nitrogen per 100 kg of grains), variable rate precision fertilizer equipment if the farmer wants to apply different rates in the field, knowledge to generate ISOXML files from the software and transfer them to the application equipment
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Connection between software and application equipment using ISOXML files to account for differences between fields and within-field variation
- **Additional requirements for application:** The method is only available for cereals and rapeseed so no combination with other crops is possible within one field.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** winter crops: cereals, rapeseed
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, oil, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** yes, applying this practice will have a positive effect on both water, soil and air quality.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** internet / data subscription costs, equipment
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Higher economic sustainability of the crop production due to higher yields and/or lower input of fertilizer.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Optimization of nitrogen supply and reduction of nitrate losses, reduction of phosphorus and potash losses.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** digestate, animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes, but subsidy rules vary from region to region and depend on the specific situation. Some examples are watersheds (drinking water production), reinforced action zones (drinking water production with breeding system).
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps

- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No, on the contrary, there are many incentives to promote this practice.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** This practice is encouraged by the Nitrates Directive
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, but it is important to increase the public awareness about the use and the advantages of these practices.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information "List of decision support tools (DST) for the management of nitrogen fertilization of crops (COMIFER)" COMIFER is an essential French association whose objective is to promote and develop contacts and exchanges of ideas between all agricultural actors and organizations in order to allow a complete control of fertilization. Link: https://comifer.asso.fr/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Liste-outils-HVE_Novembre-2023.pdf

Additional info/links:

https://agreste.agriculture.gouv.fr/agreste-web/download/publication/publie/IraGcu2414/2024_14inforapgdscultures.pdf

Practice PF n° 10

PRESCRIPTION MAPS FOR VARIABLE RATE FERTILISATION USING CROP VIGOR MAPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

*#crop vigor mapping, variable rate fertilisation; crop vigor maps;
Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)*

#PF, Food, ornamental, GP, Italy

Mappa di Vigore

Short description

- ➔ Site-specific fertilization using vigor maps is a precision farming technique designed to optimize fertilizer use, enhance agricultural yields, and minimize nutrient losses and environmental impacts. These vigor maps are generated from data collected through sensors mounted on agricultural machinery, drones, or satellites. The sensors capture detailed information about plant health using indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). NDVI measures the ability of plants to reflect light in the near-infrared spectrum, which is a strong indicator of vigor and active photosynthesis. For optimal accuracy, multispectral cameras are the preferred sensors for producing these maps.
- ➔ In the case of tree crops, drone-mounted sensors are the most effective option, as satellite resolution is often too low to provide precise recommendations for crop fertilization. By contrast, for field crops such as cereals or maize, satellite imagery can be a cost-effective solution, offering adequate spatial resolution for large-scale monitoring. Field sensors complement this process by providing localized data for specific applications, such as disease forecasting models or monitoring water stress. While useful, field sensors often offer point-in-time measurements that may not represent the overall

condition of the crop across the entire field. By integrating vigor maps with field data and soil analysis, farmers can gain a comprehensive understanding of crop health and nutritional needs.

- This technique allows for the creation of prescription maps that guide variable rate fertilization (VRF) equipment. These maps ensure that fertilizers are applied at the right rate and location, addressing specific nutrient deficiencies while avoiding over-application in areas with sufficient resources. The integration of vigor maps with variable rate technology not only improves crop productivity but also supports sustainable farming practices by reducing environmental risks, such as nutrient runoff and soil degradation. Farmers and agronomists using this method benefit from more efficient input management, enhanced crop quality, and better adherence to environmental regulations, making vigor maps a valuable tool in modern precision agriculture.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard practice in this region involves fertilization with a single, uniform dose applied across the entire field for each crop type. This approach is based on generalized recommendations rather than site-specific data, often leading to inefficiencies. While straightforward and easy to implement, this method does not account for variability in soil fertility, crop nutrient requirements, or field conditions. As a result, it can lead to over-fertilization in some areas, increasing nutrient leaching and environmental risks, and under-fertilization in others, potentially limiting crop yields. In contrast, precision fertilization practices, such as those using vigor maps, offer a more targeted approach that addresses these limitations.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Lower costs due to reduction in the quantity of fertilizer used, lower environmental impact

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Depends

on the progress of the growing season and ranges from three to six months

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes, the farmer needs decision support systems, a mobile app as well as a drone survey. An authorization for a drone flight is needed in the area around an airport or military base
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** There is a good connection between the drone survey and the mobile apps on the market (e.g. iAgro app) containing the decision support system to create variable rate fertilization maps. Transfer from decision support system to variable rate fertilizer technology can be done using different file types (ISO-XML, Shapefiles, etc.) depending on the application.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Yes, implementing this practice requires the use of Variable Rate Fertilizer Application (VRFA) technology, including machinery capable of adjusting fertilizer rates automatically based on prescription maps. This typically involves equipment such as GPS-enabled spreaders or sprayers compatible with variable rate technology. Additionally, a reliable data transfer system is needed to upload prescription maps from platforms or devices to the machinery. While the technology simplifies application, users may require initial training to operate the equipment and interpret the data accurately. Regular calibration of the equipment is also essential to ensure precision and consistency during fertilization.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** yes, in principle for all crops that are fertilized
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, ornamental
- **Influence on soil quality:** Precision fertilization improves the nutrient ratio of the soil.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, fuel, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** The use of precision fertilization has the potential to improve the economic sustainability of the crop growing. The reduction of chemical inputs in the medium-long term leads to a reduction in costs and environmental impact while maintaining the same production also improving quality and avoid over fertilization.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The leaching of all nutrients will decrease as the application rate is adapted according to the needs of the crop based on the vigor or NDVI maps.
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** digestate, animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** The measures for innovation and use of precision agriculture techniques are subject to funding at regional level.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** in Tuscany Region for Precision Farm we do not use Eco-scheme but RDP funds
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** The careful use of chemical inputs certainly helps the image of a more environmentally friendly agriculture.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** The use of innovative practices certainly stimulates the farmer and improves his image on the market.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information Agrobot Srl (www.agrobot.ag)

D2.3
Results of the GP & RI collection
process

Practice PF n° 11

PRESCRIPTION MAPS FOR FERTILIZATIONS IN VINEYARDS USING 3D POINT CLOUD AND AI ALGORITHMS ON A MOBILE DEVICE

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#3D crop characterization; variable rate fertilization; vigor maps; prescription maps; monitoring in vineyards

#PF, Food, Ornamental, Vineyard, RI, Italy

Short description

- ➔ 3D point clouds (big data) generated by the Mobile App iAgro optimize variable-rate fertilizations in vineyards. Acting as a Decision Support System (DSS), the app leverages AI computer vision algorithms, that automatically analyze vineyards digital twin and assess for canopy biometrics and field parameters. This analysis produces vigor and prescription maps for optimized variable rate fertilizations.
- ➔ The app, designed for Android/iOS systems, allows the technician/winegrower to quickly, objectively and automatically assess the spatial-temporal variability of the vineyard-covered foliage, using the cameras and GPS modules present on common mobile devices, in order to obtain an indication of the optimal volumes of water to be distributed for the rationalized application of pesticides or fertilizers. The farmer acquires, in an automatic and guided way, the images of the side wall of the canopy which

will be geo-referenced using the GPS module integrated in the devices. Proprietary in-cloud artificial intelligence algorithms are used which, once the photos have been acquired, allow to automatically determine the biometric parameters of the canopy (thickness, height, volume, LAI) and the generalized parameters of the vineyard (LWA, TRV). By entering manually some characteristic factors of the vineyard in question (e.g.: inter-row, phenological phase, disease to be prevented, etc.), the operators receive the dose of water recommended for the application of fertilizers. Another output of the iAgro app is the optimized dose of fertilizers to be distributed.

- ➔ The App, available on Apple Store and Google Play, can be installed on the most common mobile phones. Data connection is not required when acquiring images in the field, images can be uploaded later.
- ➔ The farmer can scan a part of a row or an isolated plant (in case of non-row crops) with his smartphone. After uploading the captured photos to the cloud, some minutes are needed for processing after which the 3D model (point cloud) of the scanned part of the row or tree is shown on the smartphone. The app provides the following information: canopy thickness, height and volume, LAI, LWA, TRV, optimal water dose for treatments. If the farmer repeats the scans at a sufficient and well-distributed number of points in the field (min. 5 points per field), maps of vigor (LAI) and optimal water dose for treatments or fertilizations are generated.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Foliar fertilizations at fixed doses and at periodic intervals

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?
Lower costs due to reduction in the quantity of fertilizers used, lower environmental impact

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: It's an innovative tool, at least two years are needed for the diffusion of the innovative practice

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** it needs the mobile app iAgro, reliable internet connection, basic training for the users and smartphones.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** The advisors/farmers can access through a subscription model or as part of a project initiative. The Mobile App is available both for Android and other Devices. In addition to the app, the users may require tools for data collection, such as smartphones with cameras or specialized sensors, as well as compatible farm equipment for implementing the prescription maps. Internet connectivity is also crucial for the app's functionality.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Yes, the application requires a smartphone with the iAgro app installed, a GPS module for geo-referencing, and periodic access to the internet to upload images for cloud-based processing.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** The practice is primarily designed for vineyards but can also be applied to other row crops or isolated plants, such as

orchards (e.g., apple or citrus trees), bush crops (e.g., blueberries), and greenhouse crops (e.g., tomatoes), provided the crops allow for canopy scanning and geo-referencing using mobile devices.

- **Targeted crop categories:** food, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** yes, the practice avoids over-fertilization and reduces the risk of nutrient buildup in the soil.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, loamy, clay, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, Skilled labor, Internet/data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** The practice offers several long-term economic benefits, including optimized fertilizer and water use, which reduces input costs. Improved canopy management enhances crop yield and quality, leading to higher profitability. By minimizing resource waste and environmental impact, farmers can comply with sustainability standards, potentially accessing subsidies or premium markets. Additionally, the precise application reduces labour and operational costs, contributing to overall farm efficiency.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Foliar fertilization almost deletes the risk of leaching nutrients.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** The measures for innovation and use of precision agriculture techniques are subject to funding at regional level on RDP.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No, Tuscany region does not use Eco Scheme for precision farming
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** The careful use of chemical inputs certainly helps the image of a more environmentally friendly agriculture.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** The use of innovative practices certainly stimulates the farmer and improves his image on the market.

Contact

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Eu member state: Italy (Tuscany Region)

Find out more

Source of information mobile app iAgro from Agrobot (www.agrobot.ag)

Additional info/links:

<https://github.com/ICAERUS-EU/AgroTwin>

Practice PF n° 12

REALTIME MEASURING NITROGEN CONTENT WHEN APPLYING ANIMAL MANURE TO VISUALIZE UNEVEN DISTRIBUTION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Manure nutrient content, Near-Infrared (NIR) technology

#PF, Food, Feed, GP, The Netherlands

Short description

- ➔ When using animal manure, there is often a large variation in the amount of nutrients applied over the field. Manure is transported with trucks and when applying animal manure different trucks come from different locations. Although the manure comes from the same type of animals, the nutrient content of the manure varies depending on the feed the animals ate and the intensity of the mixing of the manure. Farmers get the result of the samples after the manure is applied on the field.
- ➔ With NIR measurements, the nutrient content of the manure is measured while it is being applied, allowing precision farming as it becomes possible to apply manure based on its content.
- ➔ With NIR measurements, the nutrient content of the manure is measured in real time while it is being applied. During application, the NIR sensor emits near-infrared light onto the manure as it flows through the applicator. This light interacts with the manure, and the sensor measures the amount of

light that is absorbed and reflected at specific wavelengths. Nitrogen has unique absorption patterns, which the sensor analyzes to determine the precise nitrogen content. The data is then processed and displayed in real time, allowing the farmer to adjust application rates immediately.

- ➔ This way, surpluses can be avoided which potentially result to leaching of nutrients, soil acidification and a poor crop development. On the contrary, areas that receive less nutrients will have a reduced crop yield, lower organic matter input and overall does not reach the full soil potential. If this can be linked to task maps, the variation in the field can be reduced as the application can be adjusted based on the current situation in the field. This way, farmers will reduce costs, minimize emissions and nutrient leaching, while increasing the crop yields. Eventually, this will result in a more sustainable farming practice.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Depends on the crop. This can often be a basic fertilization with slurry with an additional artificial fertilizer.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Uncertainty in the nutrient application with animal manure. Because the inconsistency in animal manure contents, farmers do not know how much nutrients they apply, leading to over/under application. This leads to both environmental emissions and economical losses, as the yield potential is not achieved.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Once the NIR measurement is developed and installed, similar time as regular animal manure. As there is very little experience with implementing the system, it is not possible to estimate the amount of time it takes to install the tools.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** To measure the N application, a NIR measurement system is required. This includes the tool itself as the software to transform the data into useful information. When this is real-time available, the farmer can adjust the application rate while driving, resulting in a more exact application.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Yes, it should be implemented at a slurry application machine. Preferably a slurry machine that allows for variable application with a GPS system. This way, application can be adjusted based on the soil needs. But also, if this is not available, NIR measurements can still be interesting, as the artificial fertilizer application can be adjusted based on the results.
- **Additional requirements for application:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** So far limited to slurry
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes, fertilization of slurry that meets the needs of the soil.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar

- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet/data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** More efficient fertilization, less emissions/losses.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** N: Reduced, as the fertilization meets the soil requirements.
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, the practice promotes sustainable farming by reducing nutrient losses, minimizing environmental impact, and improving resource efficiency. These efforts align with societal expectations for environmentally friendly agriculture, enhancing the public perception of farming as responsible and innovative....
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, the practice can improve the farmer's self-image by demonstrating their commitment to sustainable and innovative farming practices. Successfully adopting advanced technology to optimize fertilization can foster a sense of pride and accomplishment.

Contact

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Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Source of information <https://www.cumela.nl/nieuws/nirs-technologie-voor-stikstof-werkt>

Practice PF n° 13

SITE SPECIFIC YIELD DETERMINATION IN POTATOES TO UNDERSTAND LOCAL NUTRIENT NEEDS AND SURPLUSES IN CROP RESIDUES

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#yield monitoring, variable rate fertilisation

#PF, Food, Potatoes, GP, The Netherlands

Short description

→ When reviewing the yield quantity for their potato crop, farmers usually calculate the average amount of yield per hectare of a certain field, in some cases even over multiple fields. However, the variation in crop yield within fields can be relatively large. Knowing on what spots in the field crop yields are relatively low can give insights in the optimal fertilization strategy for the upcoming year. When considering the availability of nutrients out of crop residue degradation in the following year, a lower crop yield in this year will indicate less nutrients being available in the crop residues. But a lower crop yield might also indicate a structural lower nutrient content in the soil, indicating the need for more a specific soil analysis on that location. So, insight in the crop yield over a field is the first piece of a puzzle to create the fertilization strategy of the following year. Besides, it can give insight in the profitability of less productive parts of a field. If crop yields are substantially lower in a certain part of a field, crops with high input costs might not be profitable in this site. Quantifying this data might even result in growing different crops in certain locations as the high input crop (for instance potatoes) is not profitable.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Averaging the crop yield per hectare and not linking it to the fertilization strategy of the next year and crop.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The variation in crop yield at different locations in the field can be substantial. Some parts of a field can be more fertile, have a different soil type, might be covered in shade because of trees next to a field, etc. However, the inconsistencies are hardly considered when managing and fertilizing agricultural fields. By monitoring crop yield variation within a field, farmers can gain insight in the variation of a field and take this into account the following year.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Installing the system requires time. As it is technologically advanced soft- and hardware, users need time to install this and learn how to manage this. Depending on the user, this can vary from a couple of hours to multiple working days.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** For each crop, the harvesting machine has to be equipped with a specific yield monitoring system. Additionally, the data has to be processed with specific software. If not available yet variable rate fertilizer technology also has to be acquired.
- **Additional requirements for application:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** In theory each crop that is harvested, can be measured
- **Targeted crop categories:** food
- **Influence on soil quality:** No
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, chalky, loamy, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** none
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** By knowing the profitability of different parts of the fields, the input costs can be adapted accordingly. Although models might be available to predict the crop yields, they are not yet at the level to incorporate differences in soil quality on field level
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** N, P & K: no change in the short term, although on the long term the fertilization strategy can be based on the production of each location of the field. This would mean that available nutrients would be used more precisely, minimizing leaching.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No

- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** No
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** No

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information

<https://www.proeftuinprecisielandbouw.nl/wegen-plus-rekenen-geeft-zicht-op-plaatsspecifiek-rendement-van-teelt-en-bouwplan/>

<https://www.akkerwijzer.nl/artikel/128055-fotoreportage-plaatsspecifieke-opbrengstmeting-brengt-slechtere-stukken-in-beeld/>

Practice PF n° 14

PRECISE FERTILIZER APPLICATIONS USING SOFTWARE TOOLS AND SATELLITE NDVI IMAGERY IN ARABLE CROPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Satellite imagery, NDVI maps

#PF, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Ornamental, Industrial, GP, Poland

Short description

- Polish arable farmers widely use computer programs that calculate the nutrient balance (N, P, K) on the field, and prepare fertilization plans in accordance with the principles of sustainable mineral management. Examples of fertiliser advisory applications software are Macrobil, NawSald, etc. Such tools include mineral, natural and organic fertilisers and support farmers with their proper fertilizer management and making a decision on carbon farming and eco-schemes.
- One step further is the use of satellite data to follow up their crops. SatAgro is an online platform designed for farms specialised in arable crop production which is also available in a mobile version (Android). Farmers using SatAgro can monitor their crops, implement precision farming techniques (for fertilisation, sowing and plant protection), keep records, collect and analyse a variety of spatial field data (yield maps, results of electromagnetic soil scanning, meteorological data, etc). The main source of information provided is the normalized difference vegetation index NDVI which is calculated on the basis of satellite images (observations from NASA, ESA and private operators) and quantifies the crop health and density. With its help, farmers receive information about the condition of the crops, as well as their differentiation in space and time what allows to adapt the dosage of fertilizers and plant protection products to the needs of individual field zones.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Uniform fertilization based on soil sample analyses

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Optimisation of fertiliser use, increase of yields, preservation of the environment

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: about 1 year

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The user needs a certain level of computer knowledge. Users need to pay for the software so public financial support might increase the adoption rate.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Tractor with GPS navigation that controls the operation of variable rate fertilizer spreaders. Software is needed to process satellite images and generate fertilization maps.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Internet access
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** multitude
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, ornamental, industrial, oil, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes. This practice can lead to an improvement of the soil quality as it will reduce nutrient losses.
- **Suitable soil types:** clay, peaty, sandy, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** unskilled labour, fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, fuel, transportation, storage, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Reduction of fertiliser inputs and labour inputs. Optimal fertilizers use results in an overall improvement of the economic result.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** For all of them decreasing.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes, by implementing the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice that may hinder its social acceptance:** concerns about data breaches
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes. The farmer will produce higher quality products with lower environmental pressure.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes. They take pride in managing their field and crops using digital tools and they are happy with the better economic results.

Contact

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Eu member state: Poland

Find out more

Source of information <https://www.iung.pl/>

Additional info/links:

Narzędzia wspierające, <https://dpr.iung.pl/narzedzia-wspierajace/>

SatAgro (<https://satagro.pl/>)

Elvio - Graves (<https://www.agraves.pl/elvio/>)

Practice PF n° 15

VARIABLE RATE FERTILIZER APPLICATION BASED ON NDVI MAPS CREATED WITH SATIVUM APP IN GRAIN CROPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#satellite imagery, variable rate fertilization, NDVI maps

#PF, Food, oil grains, GP, Spain

Short description

➔ SATIVUM is the free digital tool chosen by the Spanish Government as the reference farmer's digital book. It was designated as the reference tool in 2024, and it is being developed to have a wide range of functionalities. It allows farmers to register their plots, machinery, agricultural practices, create fertilization plans and follow crop development via satellite imagery. Although the tool it is only

focusing on grain crops but also horticultural crops or fruit trees, aspects related to fertilization are most applicable for grain crops.

- SATIVUM allows farmers to create fertilization plans based on different parameters such as crop needs, previous crops, potential yield, soil analysis, type of fertilizer, etc. Based on this information, SATIVUM makes a fertilization plan and suggestions on how to make fertilizer applications.
- If farmers have variable rate technology, SATIVUM has the option of creating a variable rate map based on satellite imagery. SATIVUM analyses these satellite images and creates NDVI maps that can be used to generate task maps for variable rate fertilizer application (VRFA). SATIVUM allows to create up to 7 different fertilization zones. Farmers only need to decide what is the most suitable dose to be applied in each zone.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard in Spain is to spread N fertilizer with a uniform dose on the entire plot

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The challenge is to manage nutrients in a more efficient and sustainable way, and to reduce water and soil contamination. In addition, some farmers have equipment allowing variable rate applications but not using it. This tool helps to create variable rate application maps.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: By the moment there are very few farmers doing this. Many of them have the necessary tools to do it, but it is easier to work the conventional way.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Farmers need variable rate fertilizer technology; GPS system and they will probably need to pay for some licenses. Registration in SATIVUM is free.
- **Additional requirements for application:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Conventional farming
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, oil
- **Influence on soil quality:** This practice can lead to an increase on SQ as it is expected to reduce N losses. VRFA allows to place N fertilizer in a more efficient way.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, internet / data subscription costs, Skilled labor
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** On the long term, this practice might lead to increased crop yields and/or less fertilizer used which results in higher revenue and

profitability for farmers.

- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Nitrogen: decrease
 - Phosphorus: none
 - Potassium: none

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as the practice will lead to a reduction of N losses and water contamination.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, using advanced digital tools enhances farmers' self-image.

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Find out more

Source of information SATIVUM website (<https://www.sativum.es/>)

Practice PF n° 16

NDVI-DRIVEN DRONE-BASED FIELD ANALYSIS FOR PRECISION NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#NDVI drone technology, crop health monitoring

#PF, Food, olives, grapes, citrus, vegetables, GP, Greece

Short description

→ Drones equipped with multispectral cameras fly over fields to capture images, which are analyzed using software programs like Pix4Dmapper. This software creates detailed maps that pinpoint areas needing different levels of fertilizers and water. This targeted approach allows for precise application of resources, optimizing crop health and increasing yields.

It also facilitates ongoing adjustments to treatments based on real-time data, ensuring resources are not wasted. However, the effective use of this technology depends on favorable weather conditions and requires a basic understanding of geoinformatics to accurately interpret the aerial data. Adopting this method allows farmers to enhance crop management, reduce environmental impacts, and boost productivity. Drones equipped with advanced multispectral cameras are revolutionizing precision nutrient management in agriculture. These drones fly over fields to capture high-resolution images, which are analyzed using software programs like Pix4Dmapper, QGIS (open-access platform), or ArcMap. The software creates detailed maps that pinpoint areas needing different levels of fertilizers and water. For example, these maps highlight areas with high crop production and quality and areas where crops may be struggling due to a lack of nutrients, water, or other factors. By identifying these variations, farmers can make precise decisions about where to apply fertilizers, water, or other treatments, targeting only the areas that truly need them.

The analysis is often based on vegetation indices like NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) and EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index). NDVI is a measure of plant health that uses light reflectance to determine how much light plants are absorbing for photosynthesis. Healthy plants absorb more red light and reflect more near-infrared light, while stressed plants reflect these light wavelengths differently. NDVI maps use color coding (such as green for healthy areas and yellow or red for stressed areas) making it easy for farmers to identify problem spots. EVI, on the other hand, is another vegetation index similar to NDVI but is better at capturing information in areas with dense vegetation or where the soil background might influence the results. EVI adjusts for these factors, making it particularly useful in crops with dense canopies or with significant ground cover. Together, NDVI and EVI provide a more complete picture of crop health, helping farmers monitor both sparse and dense growth areas.

→ In Greek agriculture, this technology offers significant advantages, particularly for crops such as olives, grapes, citrus, and vegetables. These crops often grow in regions with diverse soil types and microclimates, resulting in a high variability in nutrient requirements. By combining drone-based vegetation analysis with detailed soil monitoring and precise fertilization techniques, farmers in Greece can tackle challenges like water scarcity, nutrient inefficiency, and uneven yield and crop quality. Additionally, the technology supports compliance with European Union sustainability standards, such as those under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), further incentivizing its adoption.

Applying this method requires essential tools such as soil sensors for detailed soil condition monitoring, weather stations for real-time climate data, and Farm Management Software (FMS) to consolidate data from drones, sensors, and other sources. Technologies like Variable Rate Technology (VRT) and GPS/RTK systems enable precise input application and accurate field mapping. Integrating these tools with NDVI-driven analysis enhances decision-making, optimizes resource use, and improves overall efficiency.

Using this technology allows for ongoing adjustments to treatments throughout the growing season. For instance, regular drone flights can monitor how well the crops respond to an initial round of fertilization or irrigation. If the maps show that some areas have improved while others still struggle, farmers can adapt their approach by adjusting the type or number of inputs applied. This flexibility ensures resources like fertilizers and water are used efficiently, avoiding waste and promoting healthier crop growth over time. However, the effective use of this technology depends on the favorable weather conditions for drone flying and requires a basic understanding of geoinformatics to accurately interpret the aerial data. Adopting this method allows farmers to enhance crop management, reduce environmental impacts, and boost productivity efficiently.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? In Greek horticulture and orchards, fertilization practices are increasingly being refined through the adoption of precision agriculture technologies, enhancing traditional methods to improve nutrient use efficiency and crop outcomes. Traditionally, fertilization in Greek orchards and horticultural fields involved scheduled applications based on the estimated needs of the crops. This approach can lead to either over or under-application of nutrients, affecting both crop yield and environmental impact. To address these issues, more growers are turning to advanced technologies that offer greater precision such as the use of sensor and drone technologies. The introduction of these technologies is transforming fertilization practices in Greek horticulture and orchards, enabling precise nutrient management and enhancing sustainability.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Greek farmers adopted NDVI-driven drone-based field analysis to address the challenges of monitoring crop health and variability in real time, enabling targeted application of fertilisers and water. A key driver for implementation was the growing concern over soil and water contamination caused by nutrient runoff and over-fertilization, which has environmental and regulatory consequences. By reducing over-application of inputs, the practice minimizes nutrient leaching into water bodies and helps to preserve soil health over the long term. Additionally, it enhances resource efficiency and improves crop yield and quality. This approach also helps farmers meet market demands for environmentally sustainable practices and adapt to economic pressures by optimizing inputs and outputs, supported by EU Green Deal incentives.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: The implementation typically takes a few months to a full growing season. The process starts with a 1-2-

month planning phase, during which equipment and software such as Pix4Dmapper are procured, and personnel are trained. This is followed by a month-long testing phase to calibrate drones, set up sensors, and ensure the proper functioning of all systems. Integration with existing farm management systems and initial data collection takes an additional 1-2 months, after which the practice is fully operational, involving regular drone flights and continuous data collection throughout the growing season.

Monitoring measures include regular data analysis to track crop health using NDVI indices, comparing results with historical records, and conducting yield analyses to evaluate the impact of precision applications. Resource use monitoring tracks reductions in fertilizers and water, while environmental impacts such as nutrient runoff are assessed to meet sustainability goals. Feedback loops allow adjustments to operational parameters based on real-time data, with input from agronomists and crop scientists. Additionally, periodic economic and environmental impact assessments measure cost savings, yield improvements, and resource efficiency, ensuring the practice remains both economically viable and environmentally sustainable.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:**

Key logistics include compliance with Greek and EU drone regulations, obtaining licenses, and avoiding restricted airspaces. Reliable, weather-resistant drones and regular maintenance are essential, along with portable charging solutions for remote operations. Field size, terrain, and challenges like uneven ground or proximity to water bodies must be addressed to determine equipment needs. Robust data transmission and secure storage systems are critical, with offline solutions for areas with limited internet access. Seasonal timing should align with crop cycles, and trained personnel or experienced operators are necessary for managing flights and data analysis. Integration with farm management systems, budgeting for equipment and maintenance, and ensuring efficient transport across plots complete the logistical considerations.

- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Essential tools include soil sensors for detailed soil condition monitoring, weather stations for real-time climate data, and Farm Management Software (FMS) consolidating data from multiple sources such as drones and sensors for enhanced decision-making. Technologies like Variable Rate Technology (VRT) and GPS/RTK systems enable precise input application and accurate field mapping. The integration of these tools with NDVI-driven analysis enhances accuracy, streamlines decision-making, optimizes resource use, and improves overall efficiency. However, challenges like compatibility issues, connectivity problems in rural areas, and the complexity of managing multiple data streams can hinder effective integration.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Farms need reliable drones with high-quality cameras, compatible software for data analysis, and adequate data storage. Internet connectivity is crucial for cloud-based processing, with offline options for areas lacking access. Compliance with Greek and EU drone regulations, including licenses and no-fly zones, is essential, along with adherence to data privacy standards. Financially, farms must budget for equipment, maintenance, and training or hiring skilled operators. Operational requirements include designated landing areas, accurate field mapping, and integration with farm management systems. Drones should be used under optimal weather conditions (fully sunny or fully cloudy, with low wind speeds) to ensure reliable performance.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** NDVI-driven drone analysis is highly versatile and applicable to various cultivation techniques, including conventional, organic, and regenerative farming. It might optimize fertilization, irrigation, and pest control in conventional systems, support non-chemical interventions in organic farming, monitor biomass and cover crops in regenerative practices. However, its use is less relevant in controlled environments like hydroponics or vertical farming, where fixed sensors are preferred. It is particularly effective for row crops, orchards, vineyards, and large-scale horticulture, where spatial variability can be addressed through aerial monitoring.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, ornamental
- **Influence on soil quality:** An influence on soil quality can be expected from the practice of NDVI-driven drone analysis, but it is indirect and largely dependent on how the insights from the analysis are used. By providing precise data on crop health and variability, the practice can help optimize the application of inputs like fertilizers, water, and pesticides. This precision can reduce over-application and minimize nutrient runoff or chemical leaching, which in turn helps preserve or improve soil quality over time. Additionally, NDVI data can be used to identify areas of poor crop growth that may be linked to underlying soil issues, such as nutrient deficiencies or compaction. By addressing these issues with targeted interventions, farmers can improve soil health more effectively. While the technology itself does not physically alter the soil, its ability to guide sustainable management practices contributes to long-term soil quality improvement.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, silty, chalky
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, energy, internet / data subscription costs
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, fuel, unskilled labour
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Over time, the practice leads to increased crop yields and quality by enabling precise input management, improving plant health, and reducing losses due to stress or disease. This results in higher revenue and profitability for farmers. Additionally, the optimized use of fertilizers, water, and pesticides not only lowers input costs but also reduces environmental compliance costs, such as penalties or remediation expenses related to nutrient runoff or chemical overuse. Indirectly, the practice enhances sustainability, which can increase access to premium markets or certifications that reward environmentally friendly practices. Improved soil health and resource efficiency reduce long-term degradation risks, ensuring farm productivity is maintained or enhanced over time. Furthermore, adopting such advanced technologies can future-proof farming operations, attract investment, and improve resilience to climate variability, ultimately driving economic stability and growth in the long term.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The practice is expected to decrease the leaching of nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium. By enabling precise application of fertilizers based on NDVI data, excessive input is minimized, reducing nutrient runoff and leaching into the soil and waterways.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** In the EU, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) supports practices that enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental impact, which aligns with this technology. National or regional programs in Greece may also offer funding for innovative agricultural technologies. Additionally, practices tied to sustainability certifications or climate-smart farming initiatives could further qualify for incentives. Farmers should consult local agricultural offices or EU funding schemes to determine eligibility.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** There are policy barriers, including stringent drone licensing requirements, restricted airspace regulations, and the lack of clear guidelines for integrating drone data with existing agricultural policies. Data privacy and ownership issues can also complicate widespread adoption, as farmers may face uncertainty about how collected data is stored or shared. Addressing these gaps in policy could make the practice more accessible and efficient.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No.
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** The practice can be supported by Eco-schemes, particularly under initiatives that promote sustainable and resource-efficient farming. NDVI-driven analysis aligns with environmental goals by reducing input overuse (such as fertilizers and pesticides) and improving overall resource efficiency, which is a key focus of many Eco-schemes under the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** dust, concerns about data breaches, not applicable
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** The adoption of drones and NDVI analysis helps to reshape the perception of farming from traditional methods to a high-tech industry that embraces scientific advancements for better outcomes. This can attract positive attention from the public, media, and policymakers, highlighting agriculture as a forward-thinking and responsible industry. Additionally, demonstrating transparency and responsibility in farming practices can build consumer trust and confidence in agricultural products. As consumers become more conscious of how their food is produced, practices that emphasize sustainability and efficiency resonate well with public values.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Implementing NDVI-driven drone analysis significantly enhances farmers' self-image by positioning them as innovative and environmentally responsible leaders in agriculture. Embracing this advanced technology fosters a strong sense of pride and accomplishment, as farmers can see tangible improvements in crop management and sustainability. This modern approach underscores their commitment to efficiency and progressive farming practices, boosting their confidence and professional reputation. Additionally, being at the forefront of technological adoption reinforces their identity as forward-thinking agricultural professionals, further elevating their status within the farming community and beyond.
- **Other relevant information:**
 - 1) Detects subtle variations in crop health invisible to the naked eye, enabling highly targeted fertilization.
 - 2) Optimizes fertilizer use, reducing waste and lowering input costs while increasing crop yields.
 - 3) Provides timely insights for swift decision-making and dynamic adjustments to fertilization strategies.
 - 4) Combines seamlessly with soil sensors, weather stations, and Farm Management Software for comprehensive farm management.

5) Achieves higher yields with lower costs, making farming operations more economically sustainable.

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Find out more

Source of information Duan, T., Chapman, S. C., Guo, Y., & Zheng, B. (2017). Dynamic monitoring of NDVI in wheat agronomy and breeding trials using an unmanned aerial vehicle. *Field Crops Research*, 210, 71-80.

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Practice PF n° 17

LEVERAGING DRONE TECHNOLOGY FOR FERTILIZER OPTIMIZATION IN TOMATO AND CORN CROPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Nutrient variability in fields, Crop-specific fertilization

*#PF, Food, Feed, Fibre, Oil, Ornamental, Industrial, tomato crop, corn
crop*

Short description

- ➔ Fertilizer management using drones is an advanced precision agriculture technique that optimizes nutrient application, enhances yields, and reduces environmental impact. This practice integrates drones equipped with multispectral cameras, specialized software for data analysis, and precision farming machinery to ensure efficient fertilizer application. For example, a tomato farmer in Poland uses the DJI Mavic 3M drone equipped with a multispectral camera to monitor plant health and create Variable Rate Application (VRA) maps. The drone collects images of the field, capturing light in different spectrums, including near-infrared (NIR), to generate the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), which highlights variations in plant vigor and nutrient requirements.
- ➔ The process begins with the drone flying over the tomato field and capturing multispectral images at specific intervals. Using software such as DJI Terra or DJI SmartFarm, the collected data is processed into NDVI maps that identify areas of the field with varying nutrient needs. The NDVI data is then transferred to platforms like Pix4Dfields or QGIS, which generate detailed VRA maps. These maps divide the field into zones based on nutrient requirements, guiding fertilizer application. Farmers can also integrate additional data, such as soil analysis results, to refine the recommendations further. Once the maps are generated, they are exported as files compatible with fertilizer spreader systems such as Amazone Amatron, Kuhn CCI Terminal, or John Deere Operations Center. These files are transferred to the machinery using a USB or SD card, enabling the spreader to adjust fertilizer rates automatically during application. After the fertilization is complete, the drone conducts another flight to assess changes in plant health, confirming the effectiveness of the measures taken. This post-application monitoring allows farmers to evaluate the overall success of the fertilization strategy, using data collected before and after fertilization. By adopting this practice, the tomato farmer reduced fertilizer usage by 30%, saving costs while maintaining high yields. Targeted application minimized nutrient runoff, improving soil and water quality in the region. Additionally, the optimized strategy increased crop uniformity, resulting in better-quality tomatoes suitable for premium markets. The environmental benefits of this practice include reducing the reliance on heavy machinery, which prevents soil compaction and crop damage, and lowering greenhouse gas emissions by applying fertilizers only where needed. Drones can also access hard-to-reach areas, ensuring comprehensive field coverage and maximizing efficiency.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard practice in this region involves collecting soil samples and conducting laboratory analyses to determine the nutrient content and fertility of the soil. This method provides farmers with general recommendations for fertilization based on the average nutrient needs of the crop and soil conditions across the entire field. While effective for understanding baseline soil fertility, this approach does not account for spatial variability within fields, which can lead to inefficiencies such as over-fertilization in some areas and under-fertilization in others.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The adoption of this practice addresses key inefficiencies in traditional fertilizer application, such as uniform dosing that leads to resource waste, reduced yields, and environmental harm. By leveraging data-driven tools like drones and GPS-enabled machinery, it ensures site-specific application, optimizing nutrient use and saving time for younger, tech-savvy farmers. Regulatory pressures, including compliance with eco-scheme fertilizer dose limits, and economic drivers like rising input costs further motivate adoption. This practice reduces nutrient leaching, minimizes greenhouse gas emissions, and supports sustainable and profitable farming.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: The implementation of the practice typically takes around one year, which includes time for acquiring the necessary equipment, training farmers on using digital tools and machinery, and collecting baseline data such as soil and yield maps. Monitoring measures involve regular drone flights, analysis of NDVI and other vegetation indices, and periodic soil sampling to assess the effectiveness of fertilizer application and make adjustments as needed.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Drone operators must undergo special training and pass a state exam depending on the type of drone. Possibility of using public aid under Agriculture 4.0 program
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** The practice involves the integration of various tools and equipment to ensure effective implementation. Key equipment includes the DJI Mavic 3M drone, equipped with a multispectral camera for vegetation condition analysis, and a fertilizer spreader with variable application rate capabilities (e.g., Amazone, Kuhn, or Kverneland models compatible with ISOBUS or application maps). If the spreader lacks built-in GPS, an external GPS/RTK device is required for precise location tracking. Additionally, a laptop or tablet is used for data processing and analysis.
- The software required includes DJI Terra or DJI SmartFarm for processing drone data and generating NDVI maps. For creating prescription maps, tools like Pix4Dfields or QGIS are used. Dedicated software from the spreader manufacturer (e.g., Amazone Amatron, Kuhn CCI Terminal, or John Deere Operations Center) is necessary for map compatibility. A USB or SD card is used to transfer application maps to the spreader.
- The process begins with data collection, where the drone captures an aerial map of the field. The data is then processed and analyzed using multispectral indices like NDVI to generate variable field maps. These maps are loaded onto the fertilizer spreader, which is configured for site-specific application. Finally, the fertilization is executed, and the results are monitored to assess

the effectiveness of the application, completing a precise and efficient cycle of fertilizer management.

- **Additional requirements for application:** The application of this practice requires GPS-enabled equipment such as drones with multispectral cameras (e.g., DJI Mavic 3M) for data collection and GPS-enabled tractors or fertilizer spreaders for precise nutrient application. If the spreader lacks built-in GPS, external GPS or RTK devices are needed for accuracy. Compatibility between GPS data, analysis software (e.g., Pix4Dfields, QGIS), and spreader systems (e.g., Amazone Amatron, Kuhn CCI Terminal) is essential, requiring support for formats like shapefiles or ISO-XML. Training is necessary to operate drones, process data, and configure equipment, with regular maintenance and calibration ensuring reliable performance.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** This practice can be applied to various cultivation techniques, including row crops such as wheat, maize, and barley, as well as orchards, vineyards, and high-value vegetable crops like potatoes, carrots, and tomatoes. It is particularly effective in crops with high nutrient demands and variability, such as maize and wheat, where precise fertilization boosts yield and reduces costs. In orchards and vineyards, drones and sensors provide detailed insights for targeted management of individual trees or vines, while in vegetables, the practice enhances uniformity and reduces fertilizer overuse, ensuring high-quality production.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Soil quality will be improved. Lower soil salinity, increase in organic matter, better soil moisture conditions.
- **Suitable soil types:** sandy, peaty, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, internet / data subscription costs, skilled labour
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** unskilled labour, fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, fuel, transportation, storage, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** It reduces fertilizer consumption by 1/3, supports rational management in accordance with the applied eco-schemes, reduces production costs and improves product quality.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The practice reduces nutrient leaching by applying fertilizers precisely where needed. Nitrogen leaching is minimized by avoiding over-application, preventing groundwater contamination. Phosphate leaching is reduced as targeted application prevents runoff

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes. Agriculture 4.0 program.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** Existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No

- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, this practice can significantly enhance the public image of agriculture by demonstrating a commitment to environmental stewardship, economic efficiency, and technological innovation. The optimization of fertilization reduces nutrient leaching and greenhouse gas emissions, showcasing agriculture as a proactive contributor to environmental protection. Lower production costs, achieved through efficient fertilizer use, can translate into more affordable products for consumers, fostering a positive perception of farming's role in addressing economic challenges. Additionally, the precise application of nutrients helps produce healthier, higher-quality crops, appealing to consumers increasingly concerned with food safety and sustainability. The integration of advanced technologies such as drones, GPS-enabled equipment, and data-driven software highlights the modernization of agriculture. This technological progress portrays farming as a forward-thinking, innovative industry that balances productivity with environmental responsibility. Collectively, these factors strengthen the relationship between farmers and consumers, positioning agriculture as a key player in creating a sustainable future.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes. Pride in skills operated with specialized equipment.

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Find out more

Source of information <https://www.iung.pl/>

Practice PF n° 18

PRECISION NITROGEN MANAGEMENT USING HISTORICAL YIELD MAPS AND VARIABLE RATE TECHNOLOGY IN GRAIN CROPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Variable Rate Application (VRA) ; Yield Mapping ; Task maps ; GIS

#PF, Food, Fibre, Grain crops, GP, SPAIN

Short description

→ The practice of Variable Rate Fertilizer Application (VRFA) based on historical average yield maps allows farmers to optimize fertilizer use by targeting specific zones within their fields. This practice relies on precision machinery equipped with yield monitors and GPS systems that collect data during harvest. These systems record the productivity of different zones within the field, generating detailed yield maps as the starting point for VRFA.

- ➔ The practice begins with gathering historical yield data using harvesters equipped with yield monitors. These monitors measure crop productivity across the field, while GPS systems log the spatial coordinates, ensuring that each yield measurement is tied to a specific location. Farmers then upload this data to Geographic Information System (GIS) platforms such as QGIS or ArcGIS, or they can use commercial digital platforms designed to simplify the process by automatically generating maps.
- ➔ The next step is to process and analyze the yield data. Farmers, agronomists, or advisors use GIS tools to create variable rate application maps, which divide the field into zones based on productivity. High-productivity zones may require less nitrogen, while lower-yielding zones may need more nutrients to enhance growth. The practice, however, does not inherently incorporate soil characteristics or climate conditions, which can significantly affect yield data. Farmers should complement the maps with soil tests or past climate information to avoid misinterpretation. For example, a low-yielding area might result from poor soil fertility, waterlogging, or drought rather than a nutrient deficiency. Integrating soil sample results or climate records ensures more reliable and actionable fertilizer recommendations. Once the VRFA maps are created, farmers can edit or adjust them based on their field knowledge and observations. Most GIS or commercial platforms allow modifications to the map, ensuring it aligns with reality. For example, if a farmer knows a zone had low productivity due to a pest outbreak or extreme weather, they can reduce the fertilizer dose for that area to avoid overapplication.
- ➔ The final step is implementation. The VRFA map is exported as a file compatible with the farm's variable rate fertilizer spreader or precision equipment. When uploaded to the equipment's onboard terminal, the machine adjusts the fertilizer application rates in real time, based on the instructions in the map. This process ensures precise nutrient delivery, increasing efficiency, and minimizing environmental losses.
- ➔ While VRFA does not necessarily reduce the total amount of nitrogen fertilizer used, it optimizes distribution, improving nutrient efficiency and reducing potential fertilizer runoff or leaching. This results in environmental benefits, compliance with regulations, and potentially improved yields. By incorporating soil and climate data, alongside historical yield maps, the method becomes even more robust, supporting long-term sustainability and profitability for farmers.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard in the region is to spread N fertilizer with a single dose on the entire plot

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The challenge is to manage nutrients in a more efficient way, and reduce water and soil contamination

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: By the moment there are very few farmers doing this. Many of them have the necessary tools to do it, but it is easier to work the conventional way.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** Farmers need to have machinery capable of creating yield maps when harvesting and then programs to process all this data and create VRFA maps.
- **Additional requirements for application:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Conventional farming
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, fibre
- **Influence on soil quality:** The practice improves soil and water quality by reducing nitrogen leaching through precise fertilizer application. By targeting specific field zones, it minimizes over-fertilization and nutrient runoff while maintaining soil nutrient balance. This prevents nitrogen loss during rainfall and protects water sources, supporting long-term soil health and sustainable crop production.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, internet / data subscription costs, Skilled labour, Energy
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Reducing water contamination will lead to a reduction of remediation costs. VRFA does not necessarily imply less fertilizer use but it will be better used by crops. The practice offers several long-term economic benefits. By optimizing fertilizer application through VRFA, crops utilize nutrients more efficiently, potentially reducing fertilizer costs over time. Improved nutrient management also enhances crop yields and quality, increasing profitability. Enhanced soil and water quality from reduced nitrogen leaching supports sustainable farming, reducing environmental remediation costs and ensuring long-term field productivity. Additionally, the practice helps farmers meet environmental compliance standards, which can open opportunities for subsidies, eco-certifications, or premium market access. These factors collectively boost economic resilience while promoting sustainable agricultural practices.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Nitrogen: decrease
 - Phosphorus: none
 - Potassium: none

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as the practice will lead to a reduction of N losses to the environment.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information There are many different commercial platforms, e.g. John Deere Operations Center, Xfarm, Fieldview e.t.c.

Additional info/links:

<https://xfarm.ag/es>, <https://www.climatefieldview.es/>, <https://operationscenter.deere.com/>

Practice PF n° 19

INTEGRATING MULTISPECTRAL DRONE IMAGING, IOT SENSORS, AND AGRONOMICAL MODELS FOR PRECISION FERTILISATION IN ORGANIC OPEN FIELD VEGETABLE PRODUCTION

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#multispectral drone technology, crop health monitoring

#PF / food /broccoli / RI / Greece

Short description

- ➔ The practice involves integrating advanced precision farming technologies, including multispectral drone imaging, IoT soil and environmental sensors, and agronomical models, to optimize fertilization in organic open-field broccoli production. Unlike traditional fertilisation methods commonly used in Greece, which rely on the broadcast application of organic inputs like compost or manure, this practice employs real-time monitoring to address nutrient variability within the field. Conventional methods often lead to inefficiencies, such as uneven nutrient distribution, overuse in some areas, and deficiencies in others, impacting yield and environmental sustainability. By contrast, this innovation enables precise, site-specific nutrient application tailored to crop needs.
- ➔ This innovative approach combines real-time monitoring with data-driven decision-making

to ensure precise nutrient application based on the crop's specific needs. Multispectral drones fly over fields, capturing high-resolution imagery of broccoli fields to identify areas of nutrient deficiency, plant stress, or uneven growth patterns. IoT sensors installed in the soil and surrounding environment provide continuous data on soil nutrient levels, soil moisture content and temperature, and other environmental conditions. Together, these technologies provide a comprehensive dataset

that agronomical models analyze to create actionable insights, such as fertilization schedules and application rates tailored to each field zone. Farm Management Software (FMS) consolidates the data and facilitates decision-making by delivering clear, actionable recommendations to farmers.

- ➔ This innovation addresses key challenges in organic broccoli production by improving resource efficiency, minimizing nutrient leaching, and maintaining soil health. By preventing over-application of fertilizers, the practice reduces the risks of nutrient runoff into water bodies and supports better nutrient cycling. Additionally, avoiding excessive nutrient concentrations fosters healthy soil microbiomes, which are crucial for sustainable organic farming. These benefits extend to long-term productivity, making the practice particularly suited for crops like broccoli, which have high nutrient demands and spatial variability.
- ➔ One of the standout benefits of this practice is its ability to provide immediate, actionable insights that save time and resources for farmers. For instance, multispectral drone imaging can detect nutrient deficiencies or stress in broccoli crops weeks before they become visually apparent, allowing farmers to take corrective actions early and avoid potential yield losses. IoT sensors continuously monitor soil conditions, meaning farmers no longer need to rely on periodic soil tests, which can miss critical changes during the growing season. This real-time feedback enables precise interventions, such as applying organic fertilizers only where and when they are needed, reducing input costs and ensuring optimal crop health. Additionally, the integration of FMS streamlines operations by consolidating all data into an easy-to-use platform, making decision-making faster and more informed. These practical advantages, combined with measurable savings on inputs and improved yields, make this practice an invaluable tool for modern organic farming.
- ➔ To sum up, the aim of the practice is to improve nutrient efficiency, increase yield and quality, and reduce the environmental footprint of fertilization practices in organic broccoli farming. By targeting fertilizer applications to areas of need, the practice minimizes waste, prevents nutrient leaching, and supports sustainable production.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard practice in Greece, for fertilization in organic open-field vegetable production is a broadcast application of organic fertilizers such as compost, manure, or bio-based fertilizers, without precise targeting based on real-time monitoring. Nutrient application is often based on general recommendations or historical experience rather than real-time field conditions or crop-specific nutrient demands. Farmers may use periodic soil testing to guide fertilization decisions but lack access to advanced technologies like multispectral cameras, drones, IoT sensors, or agronomical models for precision nutrient management. This conventional approach, while suitable for organic farming regulations, often leads to inefficiencies, including uneven nutrient distribution, overuse in some areas, and nutrient deficiencies in others, ultimately impacting yield and environmental sustainability.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** First, equipment availability and setup is crucial, including drones equipped with multispectral cameras, IoT soil sensors, and the necessary software for data integration and analysis. Ensuring that these technologies are compatible and functional under local field conditions, such as varying weather conditions or soil types, is essential. Regular maintenance of equipment and sensors is also required to avoid disruptions during critical growth stages of broccoli. Another important consideration is internet connectivity and data

management, as IoT sensors and drone data often require reliable internet for real-time transmission and processing, which can be challenging in rural areas. Additionally, the training of personnel is critical, as farmers or operators must be skilled in using the drones, installing and maintaining sensors, and interpreting agronomical recommendations based on the data collected. Finally, the practice requires careful scheduling and planning to align drone flights, sensor readings, and fertilisation interventions with the growth stages of broccoli. Field access and mobility are also important, particularly in larger or fragmented fields, to ensure effective monitoring and targeted application.

- **Other specific tools involved/included:** The proposed RI involves the implementation of multiple tools at the farm, including drones with multispectral cameras, IoT soil and environmental sensors, and agronomical models. These tools work in an integrated system to provide real-time data and actionable insights for precision fertilization. The connection between these tools is generally good, as the technologies are designed to complement one another and share data seamlessly through farm management platforms or decision-support systems. However, the effectiveness of the connection depends on the compatibility of hardware and software, as well as the availability of reliable internet and power sources. For example, data collected by drones and IoT sensors must be processed and analyzed in tandem, and any lack of integration between these systems could create inefficiencies. When well-integrated, the use of these tools enhances the precision and efficiency of nutrient management. If not properly configured, challenges such as data silos or delays in decision-making could arise, potentially reducing the effectiveness of the practice.
- **Additional requirements for application:** Additional requirements include access to appropriate hardware such as multispectral drones, IoT sensors, and compatible agronomical software for data integration and analysis. Reliable internet connectivity is often necessary for real-time data transmission, and sufficient power infrastructure is required for charging devices and running processing equipment. Farmers must also ensure compatibility between different tools and invest in regular maintenance. Training for personnel in operating drones, setting up sensors, and interpreting agronomical recommendations is essential for successful implementation.
- **Skill/education level required:** Expert level

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** The practice can be applied broadly to open-field cultivation techniques, especially those used in organic vegetable production. However, it is particularly suited to crops with high nutrient demands and spatial variability, such as broccoli. It is less applicable to highly controlled environments like hydroponics or vertical farming, where other monitoring systems are more suitable.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food
- **Influence on soil quality:** By optimizing fertilization based on real-time site-specific data, the practice prevents overapplication of nutrients, reducing risks of nutrient leaching and soil degradation. Additionally, targeted fertilization promotes better nutrient cycling in the soil, maintaining or improving soil fertility over time. It can also support the microbial health of the soil by avoiding excessive nutrient concentrations, particularly in organic farming systems.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, internet / data

subscription costs, energy

- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, pesticides, fuel, unskilled labour
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** The practice offers significant long-term economic benefits, including increased crop yield and quality, which boost profitability. By optimizing fertilizer use, it reduces input costs over time and minimizes environmental compliance expenses, such as mitigating nutrient runoff. Improved soil health and resource efficiency contribute to sustained productivity and reduced degradation risks. Additionally, the use of advanced technologies can enhance market competitiveness, attract investment, and increase access to subsidies or certifications for sustainable farming practices.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The RI is expected to decrease the leaching of nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium. By using precision data from drones and IoT sensors, fertilisation is optimized to meet the actual needs of the broccoli crop. This minimizes overapplication, reducing the runoff of excess nutrients into the soil and surrounding environment.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** animal manure, compost, plant extracts

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** The practice may qualify for subsidies under EU initiatives such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) that support precision agriculture and sustainability. Programs targeting innovation, environmental stewardship, and resource efficiency, especially in organic farming, are likely to provide financial support. Farmers should check regional and national funding schemes specific to their location and crop type.
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Policy barriers include strict drone regulations, such as licensing and restrictions in agricultural airspace. Additionally, unclear guidelines for handling IoT-collected data in compliance with privacy laws and a lack of specific provisions for combining organic farming standards with precision technology pose challenges. Subsidy frameworks may also favor traditional practices, slowing adoption.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** The practice aligns with Eco-schemes under the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), as it promotes sustainability, resource efficiency, and environmentally friendly fertilization practices. These objectives match the goals of Eco-schemes supporting organic and precision farming innovations.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** noise, concerns about data breaches, not applicable
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** The practice can contribute to a better public image of agriculture by demonstrating the adoption of sustainable, innovative, and efficient fertilization methods. It highlights the sector's commitment to reducing environmental impacts through precision technologies and improving the quality and sustainability of food production. These advancements can enhance consumer trust and confidence in modern farming practices.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** The practice may significantly improve the farmer's self-image by showcasing their adoption of cutting-edge technologies and sustainable practices. It reflects their commitment to innovation, environmental stewardship, and producing

high-quality crops, which can foster pride in their role as forward-thinking agricultural professionals.

- **Other relevant information:** The integration of precision technologies like drones and IoT sensors not only boosts productivity but also positions farmers as leaders in sustainable agriculture. Such practices can help bridge the gap between traditional farming and modern technology, enhancing the perception of farming as a high-tech, progressive profession while also contributing to environmental goals and consumer satisfaction.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information SMARTAGRIHUBS PROJECT: FIE#26 <https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/flagship-innovation-experiment/26-fie-digitising-open-field-vegetables>
https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/Deliverables/pdfs/D3.1_IE%20Guidelines_final.pdf D3.1 P.69-70

Practice PF n° 20

LOCALIZED APPLICATION OF NITROGEN AND PHOSPHATE STARTER FERTILIZERS WHEN SOWING MAIZE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Localized fertilizer application, maize sowing

#PF, food, oil, feed, maize, industrial, GP, France

Short description

- ➔ Localized starter fertilizer applications are already applied to 75% of maize acreage in France to enhance nutrient efficiency and minimize environmental impacts. Localized fertiliser application involves applying fertilizer directly to the roots of plants at sowing, rather than spreading it uniformly over the entire soil surface. Specialized devices, such as seed drill attachments or precision applicators, deposit nutrients precisely into the soil at a specific depth and distance from the seed. This targeted approach improves nutrient uptake efficiency, reduces fertilizer waste, and minimizes environmental losses, such as nitrogen volatilization.
- ➔ The method offers several advantages, including improved nutrient uptake efficiency, which reduces nutrient losses. Localized fertilizer can be applied via specialized devices that deposit nutrients directly into the soil. This method is particularly relevant in intensive cropping systems or areas that are sensitive to excess nitrogen and phosphate fertilizer emissions. Localized application limits volatilization losses of nitrogen and improves plant access to phosphate with its low soil mobility. By incorporating this method, farmers can improve their yields while respecting the principles of sustainability and conservation of natural resources. An application at sowing maize is necessary when the residual nitrogen in the soil is less than 60 kg/ha. A dose of 40 kg/ha is sufficient to meet the nitrogen needs of young plants with up to 10 leaves. Phosphorus deficiency affects maize between the 3-leaf and 8-10-leaf stages, a period of low root colonization that limits access to phosphorus. Phosphorus is not very mobile in the soil and stimulates root growth. Integration with precision farming tools, such as GPS-guided seeders and soil nutrient sensors, further enhances its effectiveness and applicability. Additionally, adjustments for equipment calibration and placement depth are critical to ensure the success of this method. Farmers adopting this practice should monitor residual soil nitrogen levels, adjust fertilizer placement tools accordingly, and use compatible technologies for optimal results. For wider adoption, the practice can also be adapted for other crops like cereals, potatoes, and vegetables by modifying the application technique to meet their specific nutrient requirements.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Maize requires significant amounts of nitrogen after the 10-leaf stage to support its rapid growth and biomass accumulation. To ensure optimal nitrogen availability during this critical period, usually it is recommended to make the main nitrogen application between the 4-leaf and 10-leaf stages, with the ideal timing being around the 6-8 leaf stage. This approach maximizes nitrogen uptake efficiency while minimizing losses. Phosphorus requirements, on the other hand, are more time-sensitive and crucial during the early growth stages (3-leaf to 10-leaf). During this period, limited root development restricts phosphorus uptake from the soil. This early phosphorus availability is essential for root growth and overall plant vigor. Localized application of phosphorus at sowing is highly effective in meeting these early-stage requirements, as it places the nutrient directly within the root zone where it is most accessible to young plants.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Localized fertilization using seed drill technology enables precise placement of starter fertilizers, either, in liquid or solid form, directly into the soil. Fertilizers are positioned 5 cm below the seed (9-10 cm from the surface) and 4-5 cm away from the seed line, ensuring optimal nutrient availability during early plant growth stages. Thus, this practice addresses the following key challenges: 1) Conventional surface application methods often lead to nutrient losses through volatilization and leaching, reducing efficiency and increasing costs, 2) The use of localized starter fertilizers, particularly products like DAP 18-46-0, minimizes the risk of ammonia poisoning, a common issue with earlier fertilizer formulations, 3) Precise placement ensures that nitrogen and phosphorus are readily available to young maize plants, which is critical during early development stages when root systems are still limited. Additionally, the marketing and availability of advanced fertilizer formulations like DAP18-46 played a pivotal role in facilitating this shift. These formulations, coupled with improvements in seed drill technology, have made localized fertilization both practical and efficient for farmers.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor:

The localized application of solid fertilizers at the sowing of maize has existed since 2008 and was commonly used since 2012-2013. Effective implementation requires farmer training on equipment calibration, regular maintenance of tools, and soil nutrient monitoring to ensure precise application. Comparing yields before and after adoption helps validate its benefits, including improved efficiency, reduced waste, and higher yields.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The fertilizer spreader must be carefully calibrated and adjusted to ensure correct fertilizer positioning (typically 5 cm below and 4-5 cm to the side of the seed). Accurate placement is critical to maximize nutrient availability and prevent issues like seed damage or nutrient losses. Regular maintenance of the spreader and familiarity with its operation are also essential to avoid disruptions during sowing.
- **Other specific tools involved/included:** No
- **Additional requirements for application:** For the use of organic products (such as compost, manure, or other approved organic fertilizers) in organic farming, farmers need to verify that the equipment used for localized fertilization is suitable for handling organic materials, as these can differ in consistency and application requirements compared to synthetic fertilizers.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** It can also be applied to rapeseed, cereals (spring barley, wheat), beet, potatoes, vegetables and fruit trees, by adapting the form of application (irrigation, drip). It is less relevant for conservation agriculture: the level of fertility around the seed and young plant will always be much lower than in a situation where nitrogen has been worked in, but the area around the seed is naturally enriched in phosphorus and also in biological activity (mycorrhizae) which will facilitate its absorption.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, oil, industrial
- **Influence on soil quality:** Yes: in relation to a minimum 30% reduction in fertilizer use.
- **Suitable soil types:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, equipment, fuel, energy
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** The air and water quality through reduced nutrient runoff and decreased greenhouse gas emissions. Also, by minimizing fertilizer use and a targeted application, the practice significantly reduces the risk of eutrophication in nearby water bodies, which can lead to savings on environmental remediation costs.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Decrease for nitrogen (precise application reduces nitrogen runoff and volatilization), decrease for phosphorus (targeted application ensures phosphorus is available to plants rather than being lost to leaching), none for potassium.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** The practice may qualify for subsidies, depending on local modalities. Subsidy eligibility is often tied to specific environmental programs, such as watershed management initiatives (drinking water production) or reinforced action zones under the Nitrates
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** In the regional action program of the Nitrates Directive: for example for spring crops, mineral fertilizers can be applied upstream and as close as possible to sowing. For autumn crops, the application of phosphate mineral fertilizer NP-NPK in rows at sow
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** Yes: Nitrous oxide
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** none
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, the practice contributes to a better public image of agriculture by demonstrating environmentally responsible farming practices. By reducing eutrophication through targeted fertilizer application, it minimizes nutrient runoff into water bodies, addressing a critical environmental concern. This aligns agriculture with sustainability goals and showcases farmers as stewards of the environment, fostering greater public trust and support.

- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, by adopting advanced techniques that reduce environmental impact, optimize resources, and enhance crop efficiency, farmers can take pride in their role as innovators and environmental stewards. Successfully implementing such sustainable practices can boost confidence and satisfaction in their farming operations.

Contact

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Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information Localized fertilizer application at sowing maize for better initial vigour
Phosphorus at seeding provides a plus

https://naserthinking.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/STRATUS/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BDF663F24-F74A-4BF5-88D6-DFAD6232C0E5%7D&file=2nd%20sub%20Localized%20app%20maize%20vid%C3%A9o_AC3A.docx&action=default&mobileredirect=true

Five ways to localize fertilizer

Additional info/links:

Localized starter fertilization at sowing maize for a better initial vigour (2013, Arvalis-Institut du végétal article Perspectives Agricoles) https://www.perspectives-agricoles.com/sites/default/files/imported_files/398_1495209743650629746.pdf